

6G-Path

D3.1 6G-PATH experimentation environment - Initial

Document Summary Information

Project number:	101139172		
Project Title	6G-PATH: 6G Pilots and Trials Through Europe		
Acronym	6G-PATH		
Start Date	1 January 2024	Duration	36 months
Project URL	www.6gpath.eu		
Deliverable	D3.1 6G-PATH experimentation environment - Initial		
Work Package	WP3		
Contractual due date	31/12/2024	Actual submission date	31/12/2024
Type	R + DEM	Dissemination Level	PU
Lead Beneficiary	UMA	Classification Level	
Responsible Author	Almudena Díaz Zayas		
Contributors	Almudena Díaz Zayas (UMA), Jorge Márquez Ortega (UMA); Nicola di Pietro (HPE), Panayiotis Verrios, Tilemachos Doukoglou (ACTA); Jesus Macias, Arturo Torrealba (TID), Filipe Cabral Pinto (ALB), Carlos Marques (ALB), Miguel Mesquita (ALB), Pedro Rito (IT), Susana Sargento (IT), Efthymis Serpetzoglou (APART), Sozos Karageorgiou (eBOS), Jose Maria Alcaraz Calero (UWS), Qi Wang (UWS), Peter Gray (CS), Giuseppe Caso (KAU), Jonas Karlsson (KAU), Shahid Iqbal (KAU), Anna Brunstrom (KAU), Ioan Constantin (ORO), Oproiu Elena - Madalina (ORO), Taril Taleb, Yan Chen, Nora Taleb (ICT-FI), Hemant Zope (FOKUS), Dr. ing. Andreea Corici (FOKUS), Benny Häusler (FOKUS), Kalpana Chaudhary (FOKUS), Nicolas Zunker (FOKUS), Christina Lessi (OTE), João Fernandes (ONE), Luís Cordeiro (ONE), Ioannis Chochliouros (OTE).		
Peer reviewer(s)	Samuel Almeida (F6S), Andreea Corici (FOKUS)		

Co-funded by
the European Union

6G-PATH project has received funding from the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101139172.

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Revision history (including peer reviewing & quality control)

Version	Issue Date	% Complete	Changes	Contributor(s)
V0.1	21/10/2024	10%	Initial Deliverable Structure	Almudena Díaz Zayas
V0.2	28/10/2024	50% of the deliverable content		Panayiotis Verrios, Tilemachos Doukoglou (ACTA); Jesus Macias, Arturo Torrealba (TID), Efthymis Serpetzoglou (APART), Sozos Karageorgiou (eBOS), Jose Maria Alcaraz Calero (UWS), Qi Wang (UWS), Peter Gray (CS), Giuseppe Caso (KAU), Taril Taleb, Yan Chen, Nora Taleb (ICT-FI)
V0.3	04/11/2024	60% of the deliverable content	Editorial changes	Almudena Díaz Zayas (UMA)
V0.4	11/11/2024	60% of the deliverable content	Quality Assurance Review	Marilena Paraskeva (eBOS)
V0.5	12/11/2024	65%%	Add information for FOKUS testbed components	Andreea Corici (FOKUS), Benny Häusler (FOKUS), Hemant Zope (FOKUS)
V0.6	12/11/2024	70%	Added Aveiro testbed	Filipe Cabral Pinto (ALB), Carlos Marques (ALB), Miguel Mesquita (ALB), Pedro Rito (IT), Susana Sargento (IT),
V0.7	18/11/2024	80%	Updated ORO Testbed Description	Mădălina Oproiu (ORO), Ioan Constantin (ORO)
V0.8	25/11/24	90% of the deliverable content	Editorial changes	Almudena Díaz Zayas (UMA)
V0.81	25/11/24	95%	Updated ORO Testbed Description - Section 3.1.2	Ioan Constantin (ORO), Mădălina Oproiu (ORO)
V0.9	06/12/24	100%	Editorial changes, ready for the internal review	Almudena Díaz Zayas (UMA)
V0.98	19/12/2024	100%	Final version after the internal review.	Almudena Díaz (UMA), Jorge Marquez (UMA), Samuel Almeida (F6S), Andreea Corici (FOKUS)

V.099	30/12/2024	100%	Extra review of the Deliverable	Luis Cordeiro (ONE)
V1.0	31/12/2024	100%	Extra review of the Deliverable and document ready for submission in ECAS	Ioannis Chochliouros (OTE)

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
2T2R	two transmit antennas and two receive antennas
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
5G	Fifth Generation (Mobile Networks)
5G-NR	5G New Radio
5G PPP	5G Public Private Partnership
5GC	5G Core
5GQI	5G QoS Identifier
5GS	5G System
5GSA	5G Stand-Alone
6G	Sixth Generation (Mobile Networks)
AAA	Authorization, Authentication and Accounting
ADB	Android Debug Bridge
AEF	Application Enabler Function
AF	Application Function
AGV	Autonomous Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AlaaS	Artificial Intelligence as-a-Service
AMF	Access Management Function
AN	Access Network
APC	Authentication and Policy Control
API	Application Programming Interface
APN	Access Point Name
AR	Augmented Reality
ARPF	Authentication credential Repository and Processing Function
ATCLL	Aveiro Tech City Living Lab
AUSF	Authentication Server Function
AWS	Amazon Web Services
B5G	Beyond 5G
BBU	Baseband Unit

Abbreviation / Term	Description
BLER	Block Error Rate
BPF	Berkeley Packet Filter
BS	Base Station
BSF	Binding Support Function
BTS	Base Transceiver Station
C-V2X	Cellular V2X
CaaS	Containers as-a-Service
CAPIF	Common API Framework
CBS	Credit-Based Shaper
CI/CD	Continuous Integration /Continuous Deployment
CLC	Cross Layer Control
CLI	Command-Line Interface
CMG	Cloud Mobile Gateway
CMM	Cloud Mobility Manager
CN	Containerised Network
CN	Core Network
CNF	Containerised Network Function
COTS	Commercial-off-the-Shelf
CP	Control Plane
CPE	Customer Premises Equipment
CPF	Control Plane Function
CPRI	Common Public Radio Interface
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CQI	Channel Quality Indicator
CRD	Custom Resource Definition
CSV	Character Separated Values
CU	Centralised Unit
CUPS	Control User Plane Separation
DB	Database
DCU	Domain Control Unit

Abbreviation / Term	Description
DDOS	Distributed Denial of Service
DDR	Double Data Rate
DHCP	Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol
DL	Downlink
DMAP	Digital Media Access Protocol
DN	Data Network
DNN	Data Network Name
DNS	Domain Name System
DOS	Denial of Service
DOT	Distribute Organise Transport
DPDK	Data Plane Development Kit
DRB	Data Radio Bearer
DSCP	Differentiated Services Code Point
DT	Digital Twin
DU	Distributed Unit
E2E	End-to-End
eBPF	Extended Berkeley Packet Filter
ECDSA	Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm
ECN	Explicit Congestion Notification
EDGE	Enhanced Data for GSM Evolution
EIR	Equipment Identity Register
ELCM	Experiment Lifecycle Manager
ELK	Elasticsearch, Logstash and Kibana
eMBB	enhanced Mobile Broadband
EPC	Evolved Packet Core
ETSI	European Telecommunication Standards Institute
EU	European Union
eUPF	opensource User Plane Function
FDD	Frequency Division Duplexing
FR	Functional Requirement

Abbreviation / Term	Description
FW	Firewall
GA	Grant Agreement
GbE	Gigabit Ethernet
GBR	Guaranteed Bit Rate
GCP	Google Cloud Platform
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GMLC	Gateway Mobile Location Centre
GPSI	Generic Public Subscription Identifier
GSM	Global System for Mobile communication
GSMA	GSM Association
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HARQ	Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request
HSS	Home Subscriber Server
HTTP, http	HyperText Transfer Protocol
HTTPS, https	HyperText Transfer Protocol Secure
HW, hw	Hardware
IaaS	Infrastructure as-a-Service
ICMP	Internet Control Message Protocol
ID, id	Identifier
IDS	International Data Spaces
IMS	IP Multimedia Subsystem
IMSI	International Mobile Subscriber Identity
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Internet Protocol
IPSec	Internet Protocol Security
IRU	Indoor Radio Unit
IT	Information Technology
ITS	Intelligent Transport System
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JWT	JSON Web Token

Abbreviation / Term	Description
K8S	Kubernetes
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KVI	Key Value Indicator
KVM	Kernel-bases Virtual Machine
L4S	Low Latency, Low Loss, and Scalable throughput
LAN	Local Area Network
LBO	Local Break-Out
LCM	Life Cycle Management
LEO	Low Earth Orbit
LMF	Location Management Function
LoRa	Long Range
LoRaWAN	Long Range Wide Area Network
LRU	Local Radio Unit
LSP	Label-Switched Path
LSP	Link State Propagation
LTE	Long Term Evolution
LXC	LinuX Container
LXD	LinuX Design
MaaS	Metal as-a-Service
MANO	(Network) Management and Orchestration
MCS	Mission Critical Service
MCS	Modulation and Coding Scheme
MEC (or EDGE)	Mobile/Multi-access Edge Computing
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
MIRO	Multi-domain Intelligent Resource Orchestration
ML	Machine Learning
mMTC	massive Machine-Type Communications
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
MPLS	Multiprotocol Label Switching
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport

Abbreviation / Term	Description
N3IWF	Non-3GPP Interworking Function
NaC	Network as Code
NAC	Network API Catalog
NAS	Network Attached Storage
NAS	Non-Access Stratum
NB-IoT	Narrow Band IoT
NBI	Northbound Interface
NEF	Network Exposure Function
NF	Network Function
NFS	Network File System
NFVO	Network Function Virtualisation Orchestrator
NG	Next Generation
NG-AP	Next-Generation Application Protocol
NR	New Radio
NRF	Network Repository Function
NRPPa	NR Positioning Protocol A
NS	Network Service
NS	Network Slice
NSA	Non-Stand Alone
NSD	Network Service Descriptor
NSLCM	Network Slice Lifecycle Management Model
NSSF	Network Slice Selection Function
NTN	Non Terrestrial Network
O-RAN	Open Radio Access Network
OAI	Open Air Interface
OAI	Open Archives Initiative
OAM	Operation, Administration and Monitoring
OBU	On-Board Unit
OCI	Open Container Initiative
OMNT	Open Mobile Network Toolkit

Abbreviation / Term	Description
ONEmNEF	OneSource’s Microservice-based Network Exposure Function
ONF	Open Networking Foundation
ONOS	Open Network Operating System
OS	Operating System
OSM	Open-Source MANO
OSM	Order and Service Management
OVN	Open Virtual Network
OVS	Open vSwitch
PCF	Policy Control Function
PDU	Packet Data Unit
PDU	Protocol Data Unit
PFCP	Packet Forwarding Control Protocol
PLMN	Public Land Mobile Network
PoC	Proof-of-Concept
PoP	Point of Presence
PR	Performance Requirement
PXE	Preboot eXecution Environment
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
RAM	Random Access Memory
RAN	Radio Access Network
RAT	Radio Access Technology
RBAC	Role-Based Access Control
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller
RPC	Remote Procedure Call
RRH	Remote Radio Head
RRU	Remote Radio Unit
RSA	Rivest–Shamir–Adleman
Rx	Receive
S-NSSAI	Single – Network Slice Selection Assistance Information

Abbreviation / Term	Description
SA	Stand Alone
SaaS	Software as-a-Service
SAN	Storage Area Network
SBA	Service Based Architecture
SBI	Southbound Interface
SC	Software Community
SCA	Slice Controller Agent
SCP	Service Communication Proxy
SCTP	Stream Control Transmission Protocol
SD	Slice Differentiator
SDK	Software-Defined Kit
SDN	Software-Defined Networking
SDR	Software Defined Radio
SDS	Software Defined Storage
SECaaS	Security as-a-Service
SEPP	Security Edge Protection Proxy
SFP	Small Form-Factor Pluggable
SIDF	Subscriber identify De-concealing Function
SIM	Subscriber Identity Module
SIP	Session Initiation Protocol
SM	Slice Manager
SMF	Session Management Function
SMF	Single-Mode optical Fibre
SNS JU	Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking
SRAN	Single Radio Access Network
SRS, srs	Software Radio Systems
SSL	Secure Socket Layer
SSO	Single Sign-On
SST	Slice/Service Type
SUCI	Subscription Concealed Identifier

Abbreviation / Term	Description
SUPI	Subscription Permanent Identifier
SW, sw	Software
TAP	Test Automation Platform
TAS	Time-Aware Shaper
TCE	Traffic Conditioning Element
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TDD	Time-Division Duplexing
TLS	Transport Layer Security
TMF	Tele Management Forum
TR	Technical Report
TS	Technical Specification
TSN	Time Sensitive Network
TWAMP	Two-Way Active Measurement Protocol
Tx	Transmit
UC	Use Case
UDM	Unified Data Management
UDM	User Data Management
UDR	Unified Data Repository
UDSF	Unstructured Data Storage Function
UE	User Equipment
UI	User Interface
UICC	Universal Integrated Circuit Card
UL	Uplink
UP	User Plane
UPF	User Plane Function
UPG	User Plane Gateway
UPS	Uninterruptible Power Supply
URL, url	Uniform Resource Locator
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications
USB	Universal Serial Bus

Abbreviation / Term	Description
USIM	Universal Subscriber Identity Module
V2X	Vehicle to Everything
VE	Virtual Environment
vEPC	Virtual Evolved Packet Core
VIM	Virtual Infrastructure Manager
VLAN	Virtual Local Area Network
VM	Virtual Machine
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VNFD	Virtual Network Function Descriptor
VoNR	Voice over New Radio
VPN	Virtual Private Network
VPP	Virtual Power Plant
VR	Virtual Reality
Wi-Fi, WiFi	Wireless Fidelity
WWW, www	World Wide Web
XML, xml	Extensible Markup Language
XR	Extended Reality
YAML	Yet Another Multicolumn Layout
ZSM	Zero-Touch Service Management

Executive Summary

This deliverable provides an in-depth overview of the progress and status of the testbeds for the project’s initial phase. The document introduces, for each of the testbeds included, a detailed description regarding the 5G infrastructure available, computational resources, orchestration and monitoring capabilities, exposed APIs and network scenarios available for experimentation. The experimentation framework introduced in D2.1 is detailed here from the point of view of the software developed to reach the requirements enumerated in D2.1. In particular, D3.1 documents the software components integrating the initial release of the 6G-PATH framework and the components planned for the final release. The document also “outlines” the advanced experimentation capabilities embedded into the first version of the platforms to enhance experimentation features within the project’s ecosystem.

In addition, this deliverable provides the roadmap for the project’s planned evolution towards the final release of the platforms and the 6G-PATH framework. This roadmap encompasses the upcoming improvements to the experimentation framework components, addressing technical refinements and additional functionality and the development of new advanced features. These advanced features are “key” to supporting more complex and robust experimentation in the platforms integrating these features.

1 Introduction

This deliverable focuses on the initial release of the 6G-PATH framework. It provides a detailed description of each platform in the project and outlines the planned extensions and improvements for the final release.

This document details the specific test environments available across the various testbeds in terms of platforms, including hardware and software configurations, networking infrastructure, and 5G infrastructure. The testbeds are distributed across multiple geographical locations, offering diverse experimentation features and configurations that enable a wide range of testing conditions and scenarios.

The initial version of the testbeds “reflects” their readiness to support the early phase of internal experimentation using the project’s defined use cases.

The 6G-PATH experimentation framework is built on the OPEN 5GENESIS suite, constituting and implementing the framework described in the ETSI TR 103 761 [1]. The ETSI TR 103 761 is a technical report developed by the European Telecommunication Standards Institute (ETSI) that outlines scenarios and testing frameworks necessary for validating next-generation wireless communication systems, such as 5G and beyond, and ensuring that they “meet” the rigorous requirements of these systems.

Within the context of the 6G-PATH project and for the initial release of the 6G-PATH framework, the OPEN 5GENESIS suite has been extended to support the integration of metrics from Prometheus, Kafka and MQTT, among other relevant features for experimentation. The details of these extensions and the components included in the initial release are provided in Section 3. The initial release of the 6G-PATH framework focuses on delivering core functionalities for supporting experimentation, including experiment formalisation, control, data collection, and result visualisation. In particular, the components of the 6G-PATH framework integrated into this initial release represent the minimum set required to establish an operational experimentation framework across all platforms, allowing the experimentation phase of the project to commence. The 6G-PATH components are also designed with a lightweight integration approach to ensure seamless compatibility with the testbeds, facilitating easy deployment and setup.

Several advanced experimentation capabilities have been incorporated into the platforms in this initial version. The advanced experimentation capabilities refer to the specialised features and functionalities that extend beyond those available in commercial 5G equipment. These capabilities are typically the result of cutting-edge research conducted by specific groups or testbeds, or they may come from the implementation of evolving standards in the telecommunications field. Unlike off-the-shelf 5G solutions, these advanced capabilities often include custom-built network functions, novel hardware or software components, and innovative configurations that “push” the boundaries of current technology. They are designed to support experimental scenarios by integrating new standard features such as CAPIF (Common API Framework), experimental network slicing, enhanced Policy Enforcer mechanisms, close-loop configuration solutions, and AI-as-a-Service (AlaaS) features. These capabilities help pave the way for future communication technologies, including developing and validating 6G and beyond.

Finally, the plans for the new components of the 6G-PATH framework and the latest advanced experimentation features are also provided.

1.1 Mapping 6G-PATH Outputs

This section aims to “map” the 6G-PATH Grant Agreement commitments within the formal Deliverable and Task description against the project’s respective outputs and work performed. Such mapping is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Adherence to 6G-PATH GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

6G-PATH GA Component Title	6G-PATH GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D3.1 6G-PATH experimentation environment – Initial			
Reports on the activities performed in WP3. Focus on the initial planning phase for all activities and report on the activities performed to achieve the first version of the integrated testbeds and components.			
TASKS			
Task # & Title	Respective extract from formal Task/Subtask Description	Respective Chapters or Section numbers within this document addressing GA described Task/Subtask	Briefly outline how the respective document section(s) cover the described GA Task activities
T3.1-Testbed upgrades and extensions	This task aims to enhance the existing 5G pilot testbeds by incorporating the latest commercial products and open-source components that support the 3GPP standard and interfaces for both the RAN and network components.	Section 2 and Subsection 5.2	Section 2 describes the status of the testbeds, and subsection 5.2 details the planned upgrades and extensions.
T3.2 Backend components extensions	The 6G-PATH platform backend layer comprises several technical components derived from partners’ previous and ongoing research projects and products. It aims to achieve an overarching multi-testbed orchestration and management intelligent layer.	Section 4 and subsection 5.2	Section 4 describes the advanced features currently integrated into the testbeds. Subsection 5.2 describes the advanced features that will be integrated into the final release and provides the timeline for the integration.
T3.3 Southbound and Northbound	This task leverages partners’ work in previous research projects and products to evolve the existing solutions to support	Section 3 and subsection 5.1	Section 3 describes the 6G-PATH framework components integrated into the initial release. Section 5.1 describes the plan for

APIs development	the 6G-PATH requirements. This includes re-designing, adapting, and extending the Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) for automating the northbound communication and interfacing between the internal/external applications and the experimentation platform of 6G-PATH, as well as the southbound communication with the underlying B5G testbed infrastructure.		the components and updates for the final release.
T3.4 Experimentation Dashboard	This task focuses on leveraging a third-party experimentation system and a KPI visualisation system stemming from previous 5G PPP projects. This development will also account for all the necessary software adaptations to the KPI visualisation system, which should enable the visualisation of KPIs and KVs against target and baseline values to evidence incremental improvements in the infrastructure's performance.	Subsection 5.1	The experiment dashboard has been mapped into the analytics component of the 6G-PATH architecture. This component, described in subsection 5.1, will be part of the final release.
T3.5 System integration	This task will start by developing the integration plans for the two-stage 6G-PATH platform and its integration in the testbeds. Afterwards, it will be responsible for integrating the different extensions and components to release the two versions of the platform to support the project trials and pilots.	The full deliverable	The deliverable describes the initial integrations and the plans for the final integrations.

1.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The deliverable is organised in 7 sections, as explained below.

Section 1 includes a summary of what you will find in this deliverable and a presentation of the different tasks it covers.

Section 2 includes a detailed description of the testbeds, the experimentation scenarios offered, the status of the integration of the 6G-PATH framework, and a mapping of the use cases' experimentation requirements to the testbeds' features.

Section 3 describes the components integrated into the initial version of the 6G-PATH framework.

Section 4 provides the advanced experimentation features included in the first release.

Section 5 details the integration plans for the final release.

Finally, **Section 6** provides the conclusions, and **Section 7** contains the references.

2 6G-PATH testbeds descriptions

This section describes the infrastructure available in the different testbeds, the descriptions of the APIs exposed by each platform for interacting with external components or use cases, and the mapping of the experimentation requirements into the features offered by each facility.

Each subsection focuses on one of the seven testbeds. To provide a clear overview of their status, each subsection includes a figure summarising the main components of each infrastructure, the advanced experimentation features provided by the platform and the 6G-PATH framework components deployed. The components of the 6G-PATH framework are described in Section 3.

2.1 ORO testbed

Figure 1 summarises the status of ORO tested by October 2024 (M10). The following subsections describe the components, configurations, planned extensions, and how the platform fulfils the use case requirements.

2.1.1 5G Infrastructure @ ORO testbed

ORO’s testbed facility is in POLITEHNICA Bucharest National University of Science and Technology. ORO and “POLITEHNICA” operate a research, evaluation, testing, and validation environment for next-generation network technologies named “Orange 5G Lab”. This instance remotely extends to a similar 5G Lab premise in Iasi, Romania, at the “Gheorghe Asachi” Technical University of Iasi. The two testbeds are interconnected through high-speed broadband (100Gbps) and fully implement a 5G 3GPP Release 16-compliant infrastructure.

Figure 1: 6G-PATH initial release @ORO 5G infrastructure @ORO testbed

Both testbeds are equipped with the latest generation of software and hardware solutions for 5G-NR and 5GC, including open-source tools for monitoring. Moreover, they include an advanced programmable network solution based on next-generation Data Centre IPFABRIC¹ and MANO functions. The Cloud Native infrastructure

¹ For further information also see: <https://ipfabric.io/>

provides a Kubernetes and an OpenStack cluster with generous resources and high-speed networks (10/25Gbps). Both testbeds support dynamic orchestration of the network functions, dynamic slices implementation for end-users, 5G SA network services intelligent connection to EDGE computing nodes, eMBB (1500Mbps/150Mbps DL/UL), and URLLC with URLLC with <3ms one-way delay using a spectrum of up to 100MHz in the N78 band. The setup suits intensive and capacity services, demanding use cases (XR/VR/AR, Digital Twin (DT), V2X, etc.), and indoor or outdoor environments.

ORO's 5G Lab testbed is based on virtualised network infrastructure for both 5G options, the NSA and SA variants. The 5G Labs are connected to the commercial LTE Core Network for the NSA variant.

The NSA Core architecture is based on the vEPC solution from Ericsson, deployed in an OpenStack infrastructure – Orange IaaS. The existing core architecture can support broadband connectivity featuring configurable DL/UL throughput values up to ~1Gbps for DL and ~100Mbps for UL. For this existing core architecture, the 5G services are manually configured by using dedicated QoS, traffic prioritisation, private APNs, and network provisioned capabilities in terms of throughput, with the leading service being eMBB.

Table 2: Summary of the components/solutions available @ORO testbed

5G infra \ testbed	RAN NSA/SA	5GCN NSA/SA	IP Transport	IaaS	MANO & Monitoring	Security	MEC	Slicing
Bucharest	Huawei SRAN18 NSA/SA Nokia AirScale OAI / srsRAN	Ericsson 2.15 vEPC Nokia CMU23.10 5GC OAI / Open5GS	CISCO NXOS IPFABRIC	OpenStack Ussuri VMware ESXi K8s	OSM v10 Prometheus Grafana	Fortinet 1000D Arbor DDoS Mitigation	Collocated IaaS w 5G Core	S-NSSAI based APN based
Iasi	Ericsson DOTs NSA/SA OAI / srsRAN	Nokia CMU23.10 UPF OAI / Open5GS	CISCO NXOS IPFABRIC	OpenStack Ussuri K8s	Prometheus Grafana	Fortinet 1000D Arbor DDoS Mitigation	Collocated IaaS w 5G UPF	S-NSSAI based APN based

The SA Core architecture uses Nokia's 5G SA CMU Core Network solution, which runs on a virtualised infrastructure in the Bucharest 5G Lab data centre. Three main components are integrated: the Cloud Mobile Gateway (CMG), the Cloud Mobility Manager (CMM), and the Authentication and Policy Control (APC).

These components implement the 5G SA 3GPP defined Network Functions (NFs), represented in Figure 2, as follows:

- The CMM manages the Authentication and Mobility Management Function (AMF), which handles UE tracking and authentication inside the core.
- The CMG manages the Session Management Function (SMF) and handles Protocol Data Unit (PDU) sessions. Based on the QoS needs and session authentication via the UDM, the UPF is selected for data service.
- The User Plane Function (UPF) handles the data sessions payload, payload prioritisation, multi-access edge computing integration and communications to the access domain; sits inside the Bucharest 5G Lab CMG and will be locally deployed in Iasi in a Local Break-Out (LBO) approach.

- The APC manages the Authentication Server Function (AUSF), which handles user authorisation, authentication and accounting (AAA) tasks.
- The Unified Data Management (UDM) unit is a subscriber management frontend for 5G SA users.
- The Unified Data Repository (UDR) is a subscriber profile repository.

Moreover, the testbed facility supports different slices based on 3GPP NSSAIs parameters, providing eMBB with throughput up to ~1.5Gbps for DL and ~150Mbps for UL and URLLC with a one-way delay of <4ms.v.

Figure 2: 5G SA ORO's testbed architecture - General view and critical components and capabilities

The RAN consists of gNBs² supporting 5G NSA, and SA Option B. For 5G SA Option B, the gNB connects to AMF over the NG-C interface for Control Plane signalling, and it connects to UPF over the NG-U interface for user plane data transfer. The gNBs are connected via the Xn interface. The gNB provides the NR (New Radio) air interface access to the UEs. The RAN includes the Service Data Adaptation Protocol layer and the F1 interface with the Centralised Unit – Distributed Unit split. This innovative architecture provides small cell coverage to multiple operators “as-a-service” and uses virtualisation techniques to isolate data, reduce latency, and improve resource efficiency. By orchestrating lightweight virtual resources enabling efficient Virtualised Network

² A gNB (gNodeB) is a node in a cellular network that provides connectivity between user equipment (UE) and the evolved packet core (EPC). A gNodeB is the functional equivalent of a base station in a traditional cellular network. A gNodeB is responsible for radio communication with UEs in its coverage area, known as a cell. A gNodeB may be a physical entity, such as a tower, or it may be a virtual entity, such as a software defined radio (SDR).

Function (VNF) placement and live migration, it can support small cell capacity and enhanced edge cloud services by enriching the network infrastructure with an edge cloud.

Figure 3: Cloud RAN deployment in ORO’s testbed

2.1.2 Compute, storage and networking capabilities

Compute and storage resources available in the ORO testbed are listed in Table 3.

Table 3: ORO testbed resources

Capability	Per VNF (up to)			Total no VMs/CNs	Total Infrastructure Resources			MANO / ETSI	Services	Monitoring Capabilities
	Cores /VNF	RAM /VNF	Store /VNF		Concurrent VMs / CNs	vCPUs	RAM (GB)			
5G Lab Bucharest	16	32	40	200	3400	6800	8000	OSM, Rel. 12, K8s	Automation, NS	Prometheus, StableNet, Grafana

ORO testbed comprises clustered x86-server³ deployments in the two sites at Iași and Bucharest. The total infrastructure resources available are up to 3400 Virtual CPUs running on Intel 11th and 12th generation enterprise-level CPUs, more than 6.5 TB of RAM, and multi-tiered storage, with backup, fail-over, and high-availability modes integrated in a flexible, software-defined environment.

2.1.3 Virtualisation, management and orchestration

The virtualisation system available at the ORO testbed supports the fast deployment of modular services and the dynamic launch of functions in the network. The functions may be instantiated, terminated, configured, scaled in/out, and updated more rapidly than traditional physical implementations to support the instantiation of the on-demand communication service, including network slicing (see Figure 4). Network slicing supports priority management via 5G QoS Flow input, UE TCP session, and 5G QoS Flow to DRB (Data Radio Bearer) mapping. The network first maps different IP flows with the exact QoS requirements into the same QoS Flow.

³ x86 is a widely used computer architecture for central processing units (CPUs). It has become the dominant architecture for personal computers and servers. The name "x86" is derived from the 8086, an early processor released by Intel.

Figure 4: Orange 5G Lab Slicing Architecture

In particular, the tools used for the management and orchestration of the virtualisation part are the following:

- **OpenStack** is the cloud operating system that controls large pools of computing, storage, and networking resources throughout a data centre. It provides standard IaaS functionality, orchestration, service management, user application deployment, and cloud infrastructure for virtual machines and containers.
- **Docker** is an open platform for developing, shipping, and running applications. It separates the applications from the infrastructure to deliver the software quickly. An application runs in a loosely isolated environment called a container for fast-consistent app deployment.
- **Kubernetes** is an open-source system for automating containerised application deployment, scaling, and management. It is a cloud-native orchestrator.
- **OSM** is the open-source ETSI NFV Management and Orchestration (MANO) stack for E2E network service orchestration for telco services. Its key aspects are the Information Model aligned with ETSI NFV SOL006⁴, the unified Northbound Interfaces (NBIs) based on SOL005⁵, the Network Services extension across multiple domains, and the Life Cycle Management of Network Slices.

Table 4 summarises the onboarding interfaces available in the ORO testbed.

Table 4: 5G Lab onboarding platform interfaces

5G Lab testbed	Interface	Reference standards	Implementation
NFV MANO system	Nfvo_cat: management of VNF packages and Network Service Descriptors	ETSI NFV SOL 006 for NFV descriptors ETSI NFV SOL 005 for REST API for management of VNF packages and NSDs	OSM 10 NBI API for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VNFD Details • NSD Details • PDU Details
	Nfvo_lcm: Management of the lifecycle of NFV Network Services	ETSI NFV SOL 005 for REST API on lifecycle management of NFV network services	OSM 10 NBI API, for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NSLCM Details OSM based Day-1 and Day-2

⁴ See: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gs/NFV-SOL/001_099/006/03.05.01_60/gs_NFV-SOL006v030501p.pdf

⁵ See: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gs/NFV-SOL/001_099/005/03.05.01_60/gs_nfv-sol005v030501p.pdf

	and configuration of their virtual functions	Non-standard extensions for configuration of VNFs, adopting the ETSI OSM mechanisms for VNF configuration.	operations for VNF configuration.
5G slice management system	Slice_conf	3GPP TS 28.531 ⁶ for REST API to create Network Slice Instances 3GPP TS 28.541 ⁷ for the information model on network slices	Implementation in progress.

2.1.4 Monitoring capabilities

Monitoring capabilities at the ORO testbed benefit from different open software tools used for monitoring (e.g., Prometheus) and data presenting through dashboards (e.g., Grafana). The monitoring stream is focused on two main streams:

- Infrastructure monitoring involves collecting data from infrastructure components such as UE, RAN, Core Network, Transport, virtualised infrastructure, MEC, etc.
- Network and service performance monitoring, evaluating network resources, services status, and users.

Figure 5: ORO’s testbed monitoring system

The following table lists the various metrics and key data which can be obtained through the monitoring systems of ORO’s Testbeds:

Table 5: Available metrics in the monitoring system

Radio	Core	Transport	Monitoring
5G SA traffic volumes	5G SA Core REST service	Troubleshooting	Grafana

⁶ See: <https://portal.3gpp.org/desktopmodules/Specifications/SpecificationDetails.aspx?specificationId=3274>

⁷ See: <https://portal.3gpp.org/desktopmodules/Specifications/SpecificationDetails.aspx?specificationId=3400>

5G SA Call Setup	List of alarms	Ports, Interfaces, LSPs	monitoring tool
5G SA Drop Call	Root cause and Impacts	Link utilisation	Internal tools
Average reported CQI	Tree causes and impact for a specific alarm	Latency optimisation	
Average number of Users	Network performance monitor in real-time or periodically	TCEs on errors, discards, utilisation	
Physical resource Blocks Load		IP traffic usage	
5G SA average user throughput			

Configuration and measurement retrieval are accessible through a publish/subscribe mechanism for service and infrastructure KPIs, including 5G network KPIs and metrics related to computing resource consumption. These publish/subscribe mechanisms are based on a Kafka [23] bus and adopt specific information models.

2.1.5 Security capabilities

In the ORO testbed, through dynamic services instantiation, the system places the compute resources at the optimal location for processing in the distributed 5G LAB system, i.e., to the proper EDGE computing node. This instantiation is supported by implementing TMF APIs and interfaces (e.g., 5G Lab Bucharest and Iasi Implementation).

Secure access to ORO’s testbed is available to third parties from the 6G-PATH project, including Open Call third parties, via IPSec and/or VPN over Internet connectivity.

Figure 6 presents the remote access architecture for ORO’s testbed.

Figure 6: Remote access architecture for ORO’s testbed

2.1.6 Configuration and Control APIs

The ORO Testbed infrastructure is fully API-enabled. It can provide horizontal (Eastbound—westbound) integration with other ORO Testbed Instances and vertical (Northbound—southbound) integration with components and platforms of a third-party origin in 6G-PATH.

The ORO Testbed will expose three principal API categories in the scope of 6G-PATH to support OROF’s UC-EDU-1 and integration, deployment, and experimentation for third parties in the Open Calls.

The available APIs and their corresponding categories are the following:

5G/6G configuration and control APIs

These APIs are vendor-specific to the provider of ORO’s Testbed 5G/6G Core technologies. The provisional list below can be extended with more complex/advanced functional APIs.

Table 6: List of 5G/6G Core APIs available in ORO's Testbed

API Functionality / Name	API Path	Sample Calls
Next Generation (NG) Core Profiles stored in the Unified Data Repository (UDR) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>ngcprofiles</i> 	/udr/ngc-profiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> curl --include -k -L -X GET 'https://<IP_ADDR>:30106/apc/v2/udr/ngcprofiles' NG Core Profile data: curl --include -k -L -X GET 'https://<IP_ADDR>:30106/apc/v2/udr/ngcprofiles/{proflid}'
Creation/Modification of Profile <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>PutNgcProfile</i> 	/udr/ngc-profiles/{proflid}	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> curl --include -k -L -X PUT 'https://<IP_ADDR>:30106/apc/v2/udr/ngcprofiles/{proflid}' -T profile.json -H "Content-Type: application/json"
Deletion of Profile <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>DeleteNgcProfile</i> 	/udr/ngc-profiles/{proflid}	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> curl --include -k -L -X DELETE 'https://<IP_ADDR>:30106/apc/v2/udr/ngcprofiles/{proflid}'
Post – Add, Modify, Delete the list of NG Core Profiles <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>PostNgcProfiles</i> 	/udr/ngc-profiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> curl --include -X POST 'https://<IP_ADDR>:30106/apc/v2/udr/ngc-profiles' -g -T profiles.json -H 'content-type: application/json' -k -L
Returns the Universal Integrated Circuit Cards (UICCs) stored in the Unified Data Repository (UDR) database. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>GetUiccs</i> 	/udr/uiccs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> curl --include -k -L -X GET 'https://<IP_ADDR>:30106/apc/v2/udr/uiccs' curl --include -k -L -X GET 'https://<IP_ADDR>:30106/apc/v2/udr/uiccs/{uiccid}'

Examples of using these APIs include the creation, deletion, and viewing of a specific profile or a specific subscriber. The IP address of the headend is specific to ORO's internal Testbed Networks and will not be replicated for actual usage. It is shown in the list below solely as an example of the running of the API calls:

- *View a specific ngc-profile:*
curl --include -k -L -X GET 'https://172.28.22.5:30106/apc/v2/udr/1/udr/ngc-profiles/testprofile'
- *Create ngc-profile:*
curl --include -X POST 'https://172.28.22.5:30106/apc/v2/udr/1/udr/ngc-profiles' -g -T testprofile.json -H 'content-type: application/json' -k -L
- *Delete a specific ngc-profile:*
curl --include -k -L -X DELETE 'https://172.28.22.5:30106/apc/v2/udr/1/udr/ngc-profiles/testprofile'
- *View a specific subscriber:*
curl --include -k -L -X GET 'https://172.28.22.5:30106/apc/v2/udr/1/udr/subscribers/5G_SA_1'

EDGE Computing and Kubernetes APIs

The ORO Testbed exposes a collection of APIs available in the EDGE, which permit interaction with the K8s environment deployed in the Core and EDGE.

Kubernetes APIs reference documentation [15] and ORO can provide several of these functionalities, if implemented in the testbed, within a reasonable request from interested third parties.

Monitoring APIs

The ORO Testbed integrates a monitoring framework as described in Sections 2.1.4 above. The framework is available in a GCP deployment and uses industry-standard OpenGraph⁸ / Elastic APIs to expose the metrics and values. The monitoring APIs allow seamless integration with 6G-PATH's performance monitoring capabilities and permit interested third parties to view monitoring data from the testbed during their experimentation activities.

⁸ Also see: <https://ogp.me/>

However, monitoring data and output from the various network and security elements in ORO’s testbed can be relayed from the originating source, if necessary, during developing and integrating the 6G-PATH framework with ORO’s testbed.

Figure 7 provides a summary of the APIs exposed by the ORO testbed.

Figure 7: Overview of the APIs exposed by the ORO testbed

2.1.7 Description of the Network Scenarios

Regarding the 5G RAN configuration, the ORO Testbed uses the 3GPP Rel.16 5G SA option, and the configuration details are presented in Table 7.

Table 7: 5G RAN Configuration in ORO Testbed

SITE NAME	gNB ID	NR CELL NAME	NRDUCELL ID	PCI	CI	TX and RX Mode	BAND	BW
gNodeB_10_UPB	300103	gNBLAB10_UPB_indoor_NR37_1	1	110	1	4 TX and 4 RX	N78	100 MHz
gNodeB_10_UPB	300103	gNBLAB10_UPB_box_NR37_2	2	210	2	4 TX and 4 RX	N78	100 MHz

Additional parameters for the configuration of the scenarios are provided in Table 8.

Table 8: 5G/6G Feature Set of ORO Testbed

5G NF	RAN	Core	Transport	MEC
Features	NSA/SA	NSA/SA	Layer Architecture	Apps Platform
3GPP Rel15/Rel16	eNB/gNB Physical/VMs	vEPC/5GCN Virtualised	QoS/QoE Service Flow	System management
Slicing	APN	APN	QoS DSCP	E2E slicing

	NSSAI/SST	NSSAI/SST	MPLS	
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2.1.8 Mapping of experimentation requirements from the internal use cases to the testbed features

The ORO Testbed will support the UC-EDU-1 – XR Rural Schools. This use case will rely essentially on ORO’s network infrastructure. ORO will provide data connectivity through the commercially deployed network (5GSA) and access to a fully-fledged 5G/6G Experimentation Platform equipped with the latest software and hardware solutions. **During the internal trials and pilots** for the Education Vertical, the principal activities targeting the two scenarios of UC-EDU-1 will be:

- **Composition of ORO’s testbed and UC-EDU-1 to the 6G-PATH Platform**—this activity will use several Experimentation Enabling Components to onboard the required assets of the UC components.
- **Deployment of the UC components to the 6G-PATH platform**—This activity will encompass creating the Use-Cases Repository assets for UC-EDU-1, such as the Use-Case images for the Network Applications to be deployed—*Digitaliada* and third-party applications through the 6G-PATH Open Calls.
- **Testing and validation of UC-EDU-1**—This activity will be carried forward to the two test cases to validate the overall use-case ambitions and expected outcomes, supported by the KPIs and KVI to be collected during the piloting.

A high-level depiction of the overall Use-Case Topology is presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8: High-Level Topology for UC-EDU-1

The specified functional requirements (FR) for this experimentation will be mapped to the existing architecture of the Testbed and the planned extensions and upgrades:

Table 9: List of functional requirements of UC-EDU-1

FR	Title	Description	Mapping to ORO Testbed SoTA or Planned Upgrade or Extension
FR1	Beyond-5G Network Connectivity	The 5GSA network infrastructure is available, offering connectivity in the geographical areas where the rural schools are localised.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EXT1: Extend 5G SA coverage to new locations to include the geographical areas of the Use-Case beneficiaries (the two rural schools)
FR2	Availability of third-party 'XR' apps	Availability of Third-Party Apps to develop XR-enabled content, from existing curriculum Integration of Device Management functionality for the XR devices, into the Digitaliada Platform or as a third-party Application running in the EDGE.	
FR3	Availability of XR-enabled equipment	XR-enabled equipment includes VR headsets, control surfaces and interactive control devices, and the IT infrastructure required to support the operation of the equipment, such as laptop computers, tablet computers, and Wi-Fi Networks.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UPG3: New 5G XR device acquisition and validation for usage in the 6G Testbed

Table 10: List of Performance Requirements of UC-EDU-1

PR	Title	Description	
PR1	Ultra-high bandwidth	>50Gbps bandwidth available to the XR platform and UE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EXT1: Extend 5G SA coverage to new locations to include the geographical areas of the Use-Case beneficiaries (the two rural schools) UPG1: E2E Network Slice definition for UC-EDU-1 UPG2: gNBs and UPF implementation EXT2: Extend EDGE cluster to end-users service deployment location for UC-EDU-1 UPG4: 5G/6G network configuration and slice adaptation for UCs traffic requirements UPG6: Local EDGE/UPF and slice implementation, slice configuration UPG7: 5G SBA with CP/UP separation and 5G slice deployment with EDGE support
PR2	Ultra-low latency	<3ms available to UE XR devices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EXT1: Extend 5G SA coverage to new locations to include the geographical areas of the Use-Case beneficiaries (the two rural schools) UPG1: E2E Network Slice definition for UC-EDU-1 UPG2: gNBs and UPF implementation EXT2: Extend EDGE cluster to end-users service deployment location for UC-EDU-1 UPG4: 5G/6G network configuration and slice adaptation for UCs traffic requirements UPG6: Local EDGE/UPF and slice implementation, slice

			<p>configuration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UPG7: 5G SBA with CP/UP separation and 5G slice deployment with EDGE support
PR3	Near-zero Packet Loss	Minimal E2E packet loss.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EXT1: Extend 5G SA coverage to new locations to include the geographical areas of the Use-Case beneficiaries (the two rural schools) • UPG1: E2E Network Slice definition for UC-EDU-1 • UPG2: gNBs and UPF implementation • EXT2: Extend EDGE cluster to end-users service deployment location for UC-EDU-1 • UPG4: 5G/6G network configuration and slice adaptation for UCs traffic requirements • UPG6: Local EDGE/UPF and slice implementation, slice configuration • UPG7: 5G SBA with CP/UP separation and 5G slice deployment with EDGE support

2.2 UMA testbed

This section summarises the status of UMA tested by October 2024 (M10), as depicted in Figure 9. The following subsection will describe in detail the components, configurations, planned extensions, and how the platform fulfils the use case requirements.

Figure 9: 6G-PATH Initial release @UMA testbed

Figure 10: 5G Private Network at the University Campus (Málaga)

2.2.1 5G Infrastructure @ Malaga testbed

The Malaga platform, represented by Victoria Network, includes several 5G deployments at different locations: the University of Málaga, the Malaga city centre, the Malaga TechPark, and the experimental farm La Mayora in Algarrobo. This project will focus on demonstrations and trials at the University Campus and at the experimental farm La Mayora. The 5G private network at the campus of the University of Málaga serves as the central location, offering both outdoor and indoor 5G radio deployments based on Nokia radio equipment operating on FR1. Outdoor coverage is achieved through 4 microcells in band B7 (eNodeBs), 4 microcells in band n78 (gNodeBs). Indoor deployment provides coverage with two FR1 picocells in band n78. Figure 10 shows the 5G deployment in the Ada Byron building (University Campus).

Two 5G sites provide the experimental farm “La Mayora” coverage. Figure 11 provides a high-level overview of the two sites. In site 1, a microcell in band 70 TDD 3700 (3300 – 4200 MHz) with a channel bandwidth of 100 MHz and a macro cell in band 40 TDD 2300 (2300 – 2400 MHz) with a channel bandwidth of 20 MHz are available. In site 2, a macro cell in band 40 with 20 MHz of channel bandwidth.

Figure 11: 5G Private Network at the experimental farm “La Mayora” (Algarrobo)

During February 2024, the upgrade of the Nokia radios to SRAN23R1 version was completed. The most interesting features included in SRAN23R1 are the following:

- CB006878: Dynamic UL Resource Allocation in FR1 TDD Cells: This feature increases UL throughput by dynamically allocating unused long physical UL control channel (PUCCH) resources to the physical UL shared channel (PUSCH).
- CB008120: Additional Standard Slices Support: This feature extends the support of slice identifiers from non-standard values and enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) to all 3GPP standard Slice/Service Type (SST) values. The feature also introduces data radio bearer (DRB) inactivity timers, which users can set and control per slice or DRB profile.
- CB008662: Adaptive Re-Transmission: This feature improves the average cell throughput by up to 3% at a 10% block error rate (BLER) in UL and DL. It also enhances spectral efficiency and optimises the handling of the physical resources. Those benefits are achieved with the Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request (HARQ) re-transmission scheme, which adapts reserved modulation and coding schemes (MCSs) in FDD and TDD frequency range 1 (FR1).

- CB009189: Service-Aware Scheduling Request and HARQ Re-Transmissions: This feature improves end-user experience. Users can reduce call latency using several settings for data radio bearer (DRB) configuration. The feature also introduces a 5QI-80 identifier for non-GBR DRBs in frequency range 1 (FR1), 5G SA mode.

Figure 12: Site 1 at the experimental farm "La Mayora"

Figure 13: Site 2 at the experimental farm "La Mayora"

UMA's testbed is endowed with the HPE Aruba Networking Private 5G Core Network (HPE 5GC) at the two 5G private deployments described. The 5GC is the 5G network component that manages functionalities like authentication, control signalling, Quality of Service (QoS) policies, mobility, and data traffic forwarding between the base station and the networks external to the 5G system.

The HPE 5GC is a fully virtualised solution that is compliant with 3GPP and ETSI standards and flexible and adaptable for a large variety of verticals and use cases. It includes the following Network Functions (NFs): The Access and mobility management function (AMF), the Session Management Functions (SMF), the User Plane Function (UPF), the Unified Data Management (UDM), the Authentication Server Function (AUSF), the Unified Data Repository (UDR), the Policy Control Function (PCF), and the Network Repository Function (NRF). In addition, the HPE 5GC is endowed with an Equipment Identity Register (EIR), which provides a mechanism to restrict malicious user terminals in a mobile network.

Furthermore, the 5GC system exposes the following 3GPP standard-compliant interfaces:

- N1: Non-Access Stratum (NAS) over N2 between the UEs and the AMF.
- N2: Next-Generation Application Protocol (NG-AP) over Stream Control Transmission Protocols (SCTP) between the gNB(s) and the AMF.
- N3: Next-Generation User Plane (NG.U) interface over User Datagram Protocol (UDP) between the gNB(s) and the UPF(s).
- N4: Interface between SMF and UPF to allow control and user plane separation.
- N5: Interface between the PCF and the Application Function (AF).
- N6: IP connectivity to external Data Networks (DN).

In particular, the PCF is accessible to trusted third parties (AFs) via the exposed N5. External AFs can configure network parameters and perform end-to-end 5G QoS modification and control to support mission-critical services (MCSs).

Moreover, the HPE 5GC is equipped with a pre-installed instance of Prometheus, capable of exporting 5GC-related KPIs to an external monitoring system or an orchestrator. Such metrics include central processing unit (CPU), memory, and disk usage, information and statistics on processes and 5GC NFs, service usages, etc.

Finally, the HPE 5GC also provides a broad set of northbound RESTful APIs to allow external Operation, Administration and Monitoring (OAM) systems to easily integrate and automate configuration, performance, and fault management procedures.

Figure 14: HPE Aruba Networking Private 5G Core Network

2.2.2 Compute, Storage and Networking Capabilities

As previously mentioned, the Malaga testbed is based on a conglomerate of capabilities, locations, and technologies called “Victoria Network”.

Two sites can be distinguished as part of the Victoria Network, and they will be especially relevant during the execution of the 6G-PATH project.

The first site, the main data centre, is located in the Ada Byron building of UMA. The design that will be deployed is based on a hyper-converged architecture like the one shown in Figure 15.

Based on hyper-converged architecture, the following functions can be taken advantage of:

- Heterogeneous on-premises hardware is allowed.
- Only hosts and switches connecting.
- No dedicated devices for a specific task (e.g., an NFS (Network File System) server for storage); every host does a bit of everything and accesses other hosts’ resources.
- All hosts have replicated configurations. High availability through the absence of single points of failure.
- Centralised management of storage (SDS), networking (NaC⁹), and computational resources are virtualised.

Figure 15: Hyper-Converged Architecture

⁹ See: <https://www.nokia.com/networks/programmable-networks/network-as-code/network-as-code-partner-program/>

The second site is another micro data centre at La Mayora, the farm where the use case will be implemented. This site will act as an EDGE node near the customer that will be managed from the core data centre, leveraging the platform developed in the 6G-Sandbox [24] project. This platform allows us to create a trial network with components from the 6G library (Mobile Cores, Radio, Testing Equipment, UE, etc.). This micro data centre will deploy the trial network dedicated to the 6G-PATH project use case.

The summary of the resources available at the two locations are summarised below:

UMA microCPD

- Computing: 11 Hosts
- Storage: 12 TB CEPH¹⁰ Storage
- Networking: 1Gb to the Internet. 10Gb and 40Gb Internally (Management, Service, Storage)

La Mayora microCPD

- Computing: 2 Hosts
- Storage: 2TB Local Storage
- Networking: 10Gb and 40Gb Internally (Management, Service, Storage). Connection to the internet is TBD.

2.2.3 Virtualisation, Management and Orchestration Capabilities

OpenNebula [25] was selected as the private cloud manager for the micro data centres because of its capabilities and well-known flexibility.

Figure 16: OpenNebula Dashboard

OpenNebula is an open-source platform for building and managing private, public, and hybrid clouds. It provides a simple yet powerful solution for orchestrating various virtualised data centres and cloud infrastructures. OpenNebula is highly versatile and supports various hypervisors, storage, and network configurations, making it suitable for a wide range of enterprise and research environments, as shown in Figure 17.

¹⁰ See: <https://ceph.io/en/>

Figure 17: OpenNebula overview

The key features offered by OpenNebula are the following:

- **Multi-Hypervisor Support:** OpenNebula supports various hypervisors, including KVM, VMware vCenter, and LXD containers, allowing users to choose the one that best suits their needs.
- **Unified Management:** Provides a single management interface for managing virtual resources across different hypervisors and data centres.
- **Automatic Provisioning:** Automates the provisioning of virtual machines (VMs), storage, and networking resources.
- **Auto-scaling:** Enables automatic scaling of applications based on predefined policies, ensuring efficient resource utilisation.
- **Backend Support:** Compatible with multiple storage backends, including traditional SAN/NAS, distributed storage (e.g., Ceph), and local storage.
- **Virtual Networks:** Creates and manages isolated virtual networks and supports software-defined networking (SDN) integrations.
- **IP Address Management:** Manages IP addresses and VLANs for efficient network resource utilisation.
- **Role-Based Access Control (RBAC):** Provides fine-grained control over user permissions and roles, ensuring secure multi-tenant environments.
- **User Quotas:** Allows administrators to define quotas for users and groups to control resource usage.
- **Hybrid Cloud:** Seamlessly integrates with public cloud providers like AWS, Azure, and Google Cloud, enabling workload migration and hybrid deployments.
- **Cloud Bursting:** Allows cloud bursting, where local workloads can be dynamically extended to public clouds during peak demands.
- **Real-Time Monitoring:** Provides real-time monitoring of the health and performance of virtualised resources.
- **Usage Reporting:** Generates detailed reports on resource usage for billing, auditing, and capacity planning.
- **RESTful API:** Offers a comprehensive RESTful API for integrating with external systems and automating workflows.
- **CLI and GUI:** It provides a command-line interface (CLI) and a graphical user interface (GUI) for managing the cloud infrastructure.
- **Secure Architecture:** Implements security best practices, including isolation of virtual networks and secure user authentication.
- **Compliance:** Facilitates compliance with industry standards and regulations through extensive logging and auditing capabilities.

OpenNebula is becoming a reference project in cloud computing in Europe. Its European origin, compliance with GDPR¹¹, and support from EU-funded projects contribute significantly to its growth. OpenNebula’s flexibility, multi-hypervisor support, and strong community make it an attractive choice for various sectors, including research, education, and government. The platform’s ability to integrate with different storage and network configurations and its support for hybrid and multi-cloud environments further solidifies its position. As the demand for cloud solutions grows, particularly those emphasising data sovereignty and regulatory compliance, OpenNebula is well-positioned to expand its influence in European cloud projects.

2.2.4 Monitoring Capabilities

UMA has developed monitoring agents for Android devices, which are managed through Test Automation Platform (TAP) plugins. TAP, a software solution by Keysight Technologies¹², is designed to automate testing processes and is part of Keysight’s comprehensive suite of tools for electronic testing. This platform supports various testing needs, from basic device functionality checks to complex system validations and certifications.

- **The Iperf Agent for Android** is based on Iperf, a network testing tool that measures the bandwidth between two hosts over a network. In the context of Android, an Iperf agent is an app running on an Android device that acts as either the client or server in network performance tests. This tool helps evaluate the performance of network infrastructures as experienced by the device.
- **Ping Agent for Android** is implemented based on ping, a specialised tool designed to monitor and analyse network connectivity and performance. This tool typically sends ICMP (Internet Control Message Protocol) echo requests to specified network hosts (servers or other devices) and measures the response time. The primary use of a Ping Agent is to assess network latency and the presence of packet loss, which are critical factors in network troubleshooting and performance evaluation.
- **The resource monitoring agent for Android** monitors resources in Android devices, such as radio resources, CPU, memory, and battery.
- **Prometheus** is used to monitor the usage of the virtual infrastructure and the 5GC.
- **Nemo Handy** drive test tool from Keysight collects radio performance parameters on the UE side.

2.2.5 Security Capabilities

In the HPE 5GC, Transport Layer Security (TLS) certificates protect access to all exposed APIs from unauthorised entities and prevent data breaches. TLS is a cryptographic protocol that allows server identification and authorisation. It guarantees that API calls are transferred to the intended recipient while impeding data interception.

Regarding the virtualisation platform Security Capabilities, OpenNebula implements several security characteristics to ensure the protection and integrity of cloud environments. The “key” security features are as follows:

1. Authentication and Authorization:

- **Role-Based Access Control (RBAC):** Provides fine-grained control over user permissions, ensuring that only authorised users can access specific resources and perform certain actions.
- **Two-Factor Authentication (2FA):** Enhances user authentication by requiring an additional verification step.

2. Network Security:

¹¹ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation). Official Journal (OJ) L119, 04.05.2016, pp.1-88. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32016R0679>

¹² Also see: <https://www.keysight.com/us/en/assets/7018-05992/course-overviews/5992-2702.pdf>

- **Isolated Virtual Networks:** Ensures that virtual networks are isolated to prevent unauthorised access and data leakage.
- **Firewall Rules:** Allows administrators to define and enforce firewall rules to control inbound and outbound traffic to virtual machines.

3. Data Security:

- **Encryption:** Supports data encryption at rest and in transit, protecting sensitive information from unauthorised access.
- **Secure Image Management:** Ensures VM disk images are stored and transferred securely.

4. Compliance and Auditing:

- **GDPR Compliance:** Designed with features that help organisations comply with GDPR and other data protection regulations.
- **Audit Logging:** Keeps detailed logs of user activities and system events for auditing and compliance purposes.

5. Infrastructure Security:

- **Secure Architecture:** Follows best practices for securing the infrastructure, including minimising the attack surface and hardening components.
- **VM Isolation:** Ensures that virtual machines are isolated from each other to prevent lateral movement of threats.

6. API Security:

- **API Access Control:** Enforces strict access control policies for API usage to ensure that only authenticated and authorised requests are processed.
- **Rate Limiting and Throttling:** Protects APIs from abuse and denial-of-service attacks by limiting the number of requests that can be made in a given period.

All these features allow the creation of private clouds with many security advantages by default from 0 days.

2.2.6 Configuration and Control APIs

The API provided by NaC, a tool from Nokia, will be used to configure the radio. This tool enables the management and configuration of the following resources:

- IMSIs management
- Slices management
- QoS profile management
- Radio status

The HPE 5GC also provides a comprehensive set of northbound RESTful APIs to allow external Operation, Administration, and Monitoring (OAM) systems to easily integrate and automate configuration, performance, and fault management procedures. These APIs follow the OpenAPI 3.0 specification¹³ and can be consumed by any client that can send HTTP requests and interpret HTTP responses, regardless of its programming language. All network function configuration settings are exposed through the 5GC's APIs. This means that one can programmatically adjust settings, deploy new configurations, provision new users, and manage the network behaviour directly through the APIs without directly interacting with the network elements.

¹³ Also see: <https://swagger.io/specification/>

Figure 18: APIs exposed by the UMA testbed

In addition, real-time and historical data about network performance, diagnosis, and troubleshooting issues can be retrieved via APIs, facilitating proactive maintenance and problem resolution. For each network function within the system, metrics are meticulously collected and exposed using Prometheus. These metrics encompass resource consumption data, 3GPP-related metrics for signalling and traffic data, and detailed information regarding the state of the network. Further, the HPE 5GC exposes a set of parameters via API for monitoring the virtual machines. This includes metrics such as CPU utilisation, memory allocation, disk usage, networking data, and more.

Figure 18 provides an overview of the APIs exposed by the UMA testbed. These APIs are available to integrate experiment control within the ELCM [16], and the advanced features can also be utilised by third parties, such as experimenters, solutions, and service providers. The APIs exposed have already been described in D2.1, except those exposed by the Close Loop Coordinator because they are under design.

To support the configuration of radio and core parameters from the ELCM, it will develop a plugin for NaC, a Nokia Python library that enables the configuration and monitoring of the radio, and a plugin for the HPE 5GC to configure the parameters exposed by the HPE 5GC. In addition, TAP ADB plugins are already being used to control Android devices and applications. 5G routers also offer remote control features that can be used for monitoring.

2.2.7 Description of the Network Scenarios

The reference scenarios provided at the different locations for experimentation are described in the following tables:

Table 11: Band 78 configuration UMA University campus

Band	n78
Mode	TDD

Bandwidth	100 MHz
MIMO-layer	4 layers
DL MIMO mode	4x4
Beams	Single beam
Subcarrier-spacing	30 kHz
Uplink/Downlink slot ratio	1/4
Location	University Campus

Table 12: Band 77 configuration @ La Mayora

Band	N77
Mode	TDD
Bandwidth	100 MHz
MIMO-layer	4 layers
DL MIMO Mode	4x4
Beams	Single beam
Subcarrier-spacing	30 KHz
Uplink/Downlink slot ratio	3/4
Location	La Mayora

Table 13: Band 40 configuration @ La Mayora

Band	N40
Mode	TDD
Bandwidth	20 MHz

MIMO-layer	4 layers
DL MIMO Mode	4x4
Beams	Beamforming
Subcarrier-spacing	30 KHz
Uplink/Downlink slot ratio	3/4
Location	La Mayora

2.2.8 Mapping of experimentation requirements from the internal use cases to the testbed features

For the UC-FARM-1, the 5G private network deployed at the experimental farm will be utilised, which serves as the focus of the use case. This setup allows complete network control to meet the requirements of UC-FARM-1 (see Table 2). The 5G deployment operates on band 40 and band 77, and both bands will be tested to ensure they meet the performance needs of the use case. Multiple slices will be deployed to separate traffic for teleoperation commands, video/image retransmission, and sensor data. Each slice will be configured to support the specific performance requirements of the use case. Additionally, radio parameters will be adjusted to increase uplink bit rates, enabling the transmission of high-resolution images and videos.

Table 14: Performance requirements UC-FARM-1

PR	Title	Description
PR1	Smart irrigation	Connectivity density:> 100/km ² ; Battery life: > 1 year
PR2	Drones	Reliability:> 99,999%; Latency:<5ms
PR3	Multispectral camera	High uplink capacity for transmitting high-resolution images

The UC-FARM-2 5G public network from Telefonica and the Open Gateway framework will be used. The Open Gateway is an initiative from the GSMA to provide universal access to mobile network capabilities through standardised application programming interfaces (APIs). Currently, Telefonica's network APIs focus on payment features and traffic prioritisation. The second set of APIs will be used to fulfil the requirements of the UC-FARM-2 described in Table 15. In addition, the Intranet service offered by Telefonica will reduce the data path between the location of the use case and the servers hosting Terraview cloud solution. The Intranet service ensures the shortest path between the radio access and the main data centre of the UMA testbed, located at the University Campus.

Table 15: Performance requirements UC-FARM-2

PR	Title	Description
PR1	Data Transfer Efficiency	Reduce data transfer from property to central cloud.
PR2	Low latency	Enable real-time decision-making
PR3	Minimal overhead	The processing time of imagery remains the same. No increase.

2.3 OTE testbed

The OTE Lab testbed, based on 5G SA architecture, is used in UC-CITIES-2—Automated logistics. It is located in OTE’s premises in Athens, where the Radio Access Network (RAN), Packet Core, and cloud infrastructure are installed. RAN uses New Radio (NR) technology, Packet Core uses 5G Core (5GC) technology, based on Rel. 16¹⁴ architecture, while cloud infrastructure uses OpenStack Rel. 12¹⁵.

Figure 19: 6G-PATH Initial release @ OTE testbed

2.3.1 5G Infrastructure @ OTE testbed

The basic architecture designed for the OTE testbed consists of four main components: 5GC, RAN, Cloud Infrastructure and Slice Manager. Figure 20 presents an overview of the end-to-end network architecture. The testbed allows internet access and supports secured VPN connectivity for developers to access cloud infrastructure and install applications and services.

¹⁴ See: <https://www.3gpp.org/specifications-technologies/releases/release-16>

¹⁵ See: <https://docs.openstack.org/releasenotes/tempest/v12.0.0.html>

Figure 20: OTE Lab testbed architecture

For UC-CITIES-2 - Automated logistics needs, a radio access network covering an indoor area of 300m² is installed in OTE premises, while an outdoor antenna is also available. NR technology is integrated with the SA Rel. 16 architecture, and the 5G RAN characteristics are described in the table below.

Table 16: 5G RAN characteristics @OTE testbed

Type	Manufacturer	Model	Description
Radio Unit	Ericsson	ERS4408	LTE/NR TDD with four duplex TX/RX branches supporting up to 4x5 W output power
Radio Unit	Ericsson	Radio Dot	LTE/NR TDD with four duplex TX/RX branches supporting up to 4x5 W output power
Network Equipment	Ericsson	6630	Baseband Unit, 15 CPRI/9 eCPRI, LTE+NR with up to 12 CCs LTE and 12 CCs NR in dual mixed mode

NR is expected to: improve the network’s flexibility; support its high performance, and; efficiently use the available spectrum. Massive MIMO increases coverage and capacity while beamforming is also adopted.

The 5G SA Core network architecture is cloud-native and founded on containers and service-based architecture (SBA). Thus, the functionalities are handled by a set of Containerised Network Functions (CNFs) that can access each other services. This approach allows the quick launch of new services and offers enhanced adaptability. It also provides flexibility in deployment by separating the User Plane (UP) functions from the Control Plane (CP), offering the choice of either a centralised approach or a distributed one regarding the user plane traffic, thus enabling Edge Computing. A new important feature in 5G is network slicing, which establishes independent traffic flows with different Quality of Service (QoS) conditions.

The current version of the 5G networks that are installed is based on SA Release 16 architecture, presented in Figure 21.

Figure 21: 5G SA Release 16 architecture

The packet core is separated into two main parts (Figure 22): the Control Plane Function (CPF) and the User Plane Function (UPF). Both parts are implemented as OCI containers¹⁶. In the CPF component, four Network Functions are installed based on the 3GPP standard:

- Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF): The AMF component in the CPF can be accessed by any number of gNBs. Each gNB is assumed to be locally configured to access the AMF.
- Session Management Function (SMF): It can be configured to access any number of UPFs, including the co-located UPF. However, a UPF may only be controlled by one SMF. Although a gNB may connect to multiple AMF instances in different instances, each 5GS configuration containing an AMF is an independent 5GS.
- Authentication Server Function (AUSF): It enables the authentication of 3GPP access over NR.
- User Data Management (UDM) Function: It supports the Authentication credential Repository and Processing Function (ARPF), the Subscriber identify De-concealing Function (SIDF) to de-conceal the SUPI (Subscription Permanent Identifier) from the SUCI (Subscription Concealed Identifier), the 5G Authentication Vector Generation, the UE Subscriptions and ARPF to store the USIM long-term keys.

¹⁶ See: <https://opencontainers.org/>

Figure 22: Architecture adopted in OTE Lab testbed using HPE 5GC and interfaces

HPE packet core exposes the following deployed 3GPP interfaces:

- N1: NAS over N2 between the gNBs and the AMF
- N2: NG-AP over SCTP between the gNBs and the AMF
- N3: NG-U over UDP between the gNBs and the UPFs
- N4: PFCP over UDP between the SMF and the UPFs
- N6: IP connectivity to external Data Networks (DNs)

Additionally, OTE's testbed supports edge computing capabilities hosted in the cloud infrastructure. Edge computing brings application hosting from centralised data centres down to the network edge, closer to consumers and the data generated by applications. Therefore, it aims to reduce latency, ensure efficient network operation and improve customer experience.

Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) is an edge-computing architecture standard that provides computing and storage resources closer to the end user. Several architectures for edge implementation have been proposed (Figure 23). The decision about which architecture will be implemented is based on various operational, performance (mainly latency), or security-related requirements. For the needs of UC-CITIES-2, the fourth architectural approach has been implemented, where the resources are located within the core network functions.

Figure 23: 1. MEC located in the same place as the Base Station, 2. MEC is located in a transmission node, 3. MEC is situated in a network aggregation point, 4. MEC is located within the core network functions.

Edge computing is supported by providing the available resources on OTE’s cloud infrastructure, where an OpenStack Platform is installed.

Finally, a slicing mechanism is designed to offer a “key” feature in 5G networks by allowing different types of services and supporting heterogeneous requirements that could not be fulfilled by one kind of service. Multiple slices are available in the OTE Lab testbed. A slice selection mechanism is implemented using a Slice Manager, an extra software component which allows slicing. The Slice Manager is installed in the servers where the 5GC is also hosted and supports the following operations:

- Slice creation
- Slice update
- Slice cancellation
- Get the list of slices
- Get slice configuration parameters

Table 17: OTE testbed capabilities

3GPP 5G Release	5G RAN	5G Core	Network Slicing	MEC	Virtualized Infra	5G Security
Rel. 16	Ericsson NR, with both indoor and outdoor coverage	HPE SA Rel. 16	Supported. Multiple slices could be created in advance. Slice selection could be dynamic.		IaaS	

2.3.2 Compute, Storage and Networking Capabilities

The network components used in the testbed’s current version are installed in generic servers. More specifically, 5GC is provided by Hewlett Packard Enterprise (HPE), using the network functions implementation approach, using the network functions implementation approach installed in an ESXI Platform release 7.0.1¹⁷ hosted in a Dell R640 server¹⁸. Its available resources are 2x Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 6138 CPU at 2.00GHz, 352 GB DDR RAM and storage of 1TB SATA and 8TB SAS.

Additionally, the cloud infrastructure consists of Dell servers with 4 vCPUs, 8 GB RAM, and 50GB storage installed with Red Hat OpenStack Platform release 16.1.8¹⁹.

Table 18 shows that the testbed’s capabilities include network slicing, MEC (utilising cloud resources), and security.

Table 18: Testbed resources

VNF capabilities	Total Virtualized Infrastructure resources	MANO
Cores: 4	CPU: 4	OSM Rel. 12
RAM: 8 GB	RAM: 8GB	
Storage: 40 GB	Storage: 40GB	

2.3.3 Virtualisation, Management and Orchestration

The Open-Source MANO (OSM) has been used for the orchestration of the OTE testbed. The design-time scope of OSM includes (i) the capability to Create/Read/Update/Delete operations on the Network Service definition and; (ii) tools for VNF Package Generation. On the other hand, the run-time scope of OSM mainly provides: (i) an automated Service Orchestration environment as the central coordination engine; (ii) plugins for integrating multiple Virtual Infrastructure Managers - VIMs (including OpenStack, VMWare, OpenVIM) and Kubernetes Clusters; (iii) support to integrate Physical Network Functions into Network Services. The OSM Release 12²⁰ will be used for the 6G-PATH project, which includes relevant features in the direction of increased compliance with the ETSI NFV standards:

- Scaling for Kubernetes Applications, which improves scalability in Kubernetes deployments.
- Reduced footprint and improved release process, relying on Python packages with locked dependency versions and significantly reduced image sizes.

2.3.4 Monitoring Capabilities

The OTE testbeds integrate case-specific monitoring tools. For the use case CITIES-2-Automated Logistics, the VIAVI NITRO software platform²¹ will be used. The application and the software probe, integrating the monitoring solution, will be installed on VMs (Fusion Controller, Fusion ESAM to manage Smart SFPs: JMEPs, Fusion Analytics, software probe vPMA for TWAMP initiation). Hardware probes and JMEP Smart SFP will also be installed in various network parts.

¹⁷ Also see: <https://docs.vmware.com/en/VMware-vSphere/7.0/rn/vsphere-esxi-701-release-notes.html>

¹⁸ See: <https://www.dell.com/us-en/work/shop/povw/poweredge-r640>

¹⁹ See, *inter-alia*: https://docs.redhat.com/en/documentation/red_hat_openstack_platform/16.1/html-single/release_notes/index#making-open-source-more-inclusive

²⁰ See: https://osm-download.etsi.org/ftp/osm-12.0-twelve/OSM_Release_TWELVE_Release_Notes.pdf

²¹ See: <https://www.viavisolutions.com/en-us/solutions/nitro>

A KAFKA interface²² will be activated to transfer measurement data to the ELCM.

The application GUI specifies the measurement scenarios, runs them, and gets results. The output obtained is the network performance measurements. The commercial VIAVI NITRO SW platform²³ (FUSION application [28]) is used.

The monitoring system comprises hardware and software probes that gather measurement data and a central application that collects and presents the data.

ACTA, as the tests are generated, will provide detailed monitoring metrics in the 5G infrastructure end-to-end, as well as segments of the network. This supports a better understanding of success segments or pain areas. The approach provides better network visibility for troubleshooting. The solution remotely tests new service activation, performance monitoring, and troubleshooting. Various hardware and software, open source and proprietary, probes will be used. ACTA will also identify the probes' configuration to match the interfaces & placement location with that of the network links and interfaces. The target is to achieve end-to-end measurement of Network KPI values and measurements in network segments, i.e. RAN and transport.

ACTA has developed Python code for a TWAMP implementation, which can optionally be used on mobile devices to provide monitoring data from the end-user's point of view.

The KMaP is the central management platform for collecting measurement data from the probes, which is installed in the network and is responsible for collecting data from measurements of network KPIs. The system accumulates over 150 metrics at various points of a Live Network.

Data collection is an automated process running 24/7, with a 1 min monitoring granularity and a 10ms sampling granularity. Thresholds can be set to allow for a cockpit view of KPIs in accordance with the designated performance targets.

The KPI metrics measured are latency, packet loss, packet delay, frame loss, traffic throughput, one-way results (from one network location towards another point), and two-way results (from one network location to another point and back to the initial point).

An example showing parts of the GUI is displayed in Figure 24 and Figure 25.

²² See: <https://kafka.apache.org/>

²³ The VIAVI Network Integrated Test, Real-time analytics and Optimisation (NITRO) solution is the first real-time intelligence platform that connects testing and service activation data from instruments with software-based planning, provisioning, assurance and optimisation probes and applications, working seamlessly across mobile, fiber, cable, cloud and enterprise networks. For further information also see: <https://www.viavisolutions.com/en-us/solutions/nitro>

Figure 24: Application dashboard @OTE testbed

Figure 25: Monitoring measurement @OTE testbed

2.3.5 Security Capabilities

To use the network services, UEs must follow the registration process defined by 5G technology. At the same time, developers are not allowed access, as this is a closed network that only authorised network engineers have access to. Developers can access the cloud infrastructure to install applications that will be exploited by the use cases only by using a VPN account, the credentials of which are created and provided by OTE.

2.3.6 Configuration and Control APIs

Network components are installed in the testbed to allow connectivity and support for the automated logistics applications. These components will be interconnected with external tools, such as monitoring tools and cloud-based applications. To complete the end-to-end integration of the network with the external components, several standard and custom interfaces will be deployed, as presented in Figure 26.

Figure 26: Control and configuration interfaces @OTE testbed

Especially for the Slice Manager integration, its southbound interface interacts with the slice plugins deployed in the 5G testbed adopting the following APIs:

- Authentication to the 5G Core

To get the authentication token from the 5G Core, the plugin implements the following API, which can be showcased with the following curl command:

```
curl--location--request POST 'https://5gcore_api_endpoint/api/1/auth/login' \
--header 'Content-Type: application/json' \
--data-raw '{
"username": "USERNAME_HERE",
"password": "PASSWORD_HERE"
}'
```

The plugin looks for the ACCESS_TOKEN in the response to the POST request, as shown in the following example.

```
curl --location --request GET 'ENDPOINT' --header 'Authorization: Bearer ACCESS_TOKEN_HERE'
```

After getting an authentication token, the system can make subsequent requests.

- Retrieve the Provisioned Data profiles list

The plugin uses the following API to retrieve the complete list of Provisioned Data Profiles:

```
curl -k -X GET "https://5gcore_api_endpoint/api/1/provisioning/provisioned_data_profiles"
```

- Retrieve Single Provisioned Data profile info

The following API retrieves information on a specific provisioned Profile:

```
curl -k -X GET "https://5gcore_api_endpoint/api/1/provisioning/provisioned_data_profiles/{uuid}"
```

In the current example, {uuid} is changed with the required UUID address.

- Delete Single Provisioned Data profiles

The following API allows the delete of an existing Provisioned Data Profile

```
curl -k -X DELETE "https://5gcore_api_endpoint/api/1/provisioning/provisioned_data_profiles/{uuid}"
```

In the current example {uuid} is a placeholder and changed with the required UUID address.

- *Create a new Provisioned Data Profile*

The following API creates a new Provisioned Data Profile.

```
curl -k -X POST "https://5gcore_api_endpoint/api/1/provisioning/provisioned_data_profiles"
```

- Replace (or create) a new Provisioned Data Profile

This API replaces an existing Provisioned Data profile (or creates a new one if it doesn't exist).

```
curl -k -X PUT "https://5gcore_api_endpoint/api/1/provisioning/provisioned_data_profiles" -H "Content-Type: application/json" -d @./provisioned_data_profile_replace.json
```

- Retrieve a PLMN rule for an existing Provisioned Data Profile

This API retrieves the rule for a specific PLMN of an existing provisioned data profile

```
curl -k -X GET "https://5gcore_api_endpoint/api/1/provisioning/provisioned_data_profiles/{uuid}/{plmn}"
```

In the current example, {uuid} and {plmn} are changed to the required uuid and plmn values.

- Create or replace a PLMN rule for an existing Provisioned Data Profile

This API creates a new rule (or replaces an existing one) for a specific PLMN for an existing Provisioned Data Profile.

```
curl -k -X PUT "https://5gcore_api_endpoint/api/1/provisioning/provisioned_data_profiles/{uuid}/{plmn}"
```

- Delete a PLMN Rule for a Provisioned Data Profile

This API deletes an existing PLMN rule for a Provisioned Data Profile.

```
curl -k -X DELETE "https://5gcore_api_endpoint/api/1/provisioning/provisioned_data_profiles/{uuid}/{plmn}"
```

In the current example, {uuid} and {plmn} are changed to the required uuid and plmn values.

- Policy associated with an existing SUPI

This API replaces the policy data profile associated with an existing SUPI:

```
curl -k -X PUT "https://5gcore_api_endpoint/api/1/provisioning/supis/{supi}/policy_data_profile"
```

In the current example {SUPI} is a placeholder. Change it with the desired SUPI.

- Replace the provisioned Data Profile associated with an existing SUPI

This API replaces the provisioned data profile associated with an existing SUPI:

```
curl -k -X PUT "https://5gcore_api_endpoint/api/1/provisioning/supis/{supi}/provisioned_data_profile"
```

In the current example {SUPI} is a placeholder. It should be changed with the desired SUPI.

2.3.7 Description of the Network Scenarios

RAN, Core, Virtualisation, and orchestration are used in the OTE testbed to offer 5G SA services and slicing. Table 19 describes the technical details of the RAN configurations.

Table 19: Network configuration offered by the testbed

Band	N78
Mode	TDD
Bandwidth	100 MHz
MIMO-layer	1 layer
DL MIMO mode	2x2
Beams	Single beam
Location	OTE lab premises

The 5G testbed can provide one or more slice instances of one or more types. A slice type is identified by an S-NSSAI, composed of a Slice Service Type, SST, and optionally a Slice Differentiator, SD. Each slice instance is realized by assigning the network functions within each 5G core system to specific S-NSSAI through appropriate configuration. A UE can access any number of slice instances in the network. The UPFs provide access to one or more external Data Networks through Data Network Names (DNNs) that are unique to each slice instance. At the same time, it is possible to provide the same name to access different Data Networks in different slice instances.

The following options are available in the OTE Lab testbed:

- Configure one or more slices per subscriber.
- The subscriber can be registered and use one or more slices at the same time.
- UPF can be selected on a slice base. Different slices can be associated with different UPFs.
- One UPF can be dedicated or shared among several slices.

2.3.8 Mapping of experimentation requirements from the internal use cases to the testbed features

The OTE Lab testbed will be used in UC-Cities-2 - Automated logistics to support Industry 4.0 vertical requirements. It will offer network capabilities such as Network Function Virtualization Management and Orchestration, network slicing and Slice Management, and monitoring of the network KPIs (throughput, latency, packet loss, jitter).

Industrial environments like logistics warehouses are set to be transformed by autonomous robots, such as Autonomous Guided Vehicles (AGV). The target of using AGVs is dual: to enhance safety by reducing manual handling risks and significantly boost productivity. AGVs will be equipped with advanced sensors and cameras to communicate seamlessly with a central control platform. This communication is facilitated by cutting-edge B5G networking, ensuring real-time data exchange and optimal performance:

- High network reliability and availability are essential for maintaining constant remote control of the AGV by a human operator.
- High throughput since video streaming should be sent to the remote operator.
- High device density must be supported so that the AGV sensors can detect other objects or people and estimate their distance to avoid accidents in an industrial environment.
- Leveraging heterogeneous data sources is crucial for optimising AGV routes and minimising process time. This includes real-time information on product location, current AGV position, and its designated destination.

The UC-Cities-2—Automated logistics functional and performance requirements have been identified and are presented in Table 20 and Table 21.

Table 20: UC-Cities-2 functional requirements

FR	Title	Description
FR1	Video & Data transfer	AGV should be able to send information about the environment using sensors and video cameras.
FR2	Autonomy	AGV should be able to move autonomously, avoiding obstacles and paying extra attention to humans moving on the same area.
FR3	Security	The network will provide authentication of the devices that are registered in the network.

Table 21: UC-Cities-2 performance requirements

PR	Title	Description
PR1	Availability	High availability (99,999%) required, so that the human AGV operator should be able to reach, and control AGV if necessary.
PR2	Reliability	Same as above for availability (99,999%).
PR3	Latency	Low in order to enhance perceived quality of service. (<5ms)
PR4	Throughput	High to be able to stream video and transfer sensors data. (1Gbps DL, 100Mbps UL)
PR5	Density	Number of sensors/cameras per sqm (25 devices per 100m ²)

2.4 UWS testbed

Figure 27 maps the current components in the UWS testbed to the reference architecture blocks (in grey) defined in the project. The purple blocks indicate components to be integrated from the project in the first stage to enable the onboarding and testing of the use case. Additional elements, e.g., more advanced experimentation features, may be added with the help of the project partners. Existing components are subject to further enhancements and new development, e.g., by integrating relevant components developed/recommended in the project.

Figure 27: 6G-PATH Initial Release @UWS testbed

2.4.1 5G Infrastructure @UWX testbed

The Beyond 5G Testbed is in room E354 at Paisley Campus, University of the West of Scotland, Paisley, Scotland, United Kingdom. It consists of two different sets of machines: those composing the managed infrastructure and those used for managing such infrastructure. The University of the West of Scotland owns the Beyond 5G Testbed, and the Beyond 5G Team operates it.

Figure 28 shows the topology for the UWS infrastructure, consisting of several layers, including cloud-managed infrastructure (edge and core), Transport, Management and control, and Interdomain (Access layer) for Internet access outside the university. It is noted that edge nodes are deployed in the infrastructure, which will be further developed to support the demanding XR application in this use case. RAN capabilities are subject to upgrading to offer more reliable and capable performance in line with beyond 5G (towards 6G) expectations.

Two different 5G software are installed: “Open Air Interface 4G RAN” and “Open Air Interface 5G RAN”, with versions 2023.w42 and 2023.w42, respectively. Only one can be instantiated at a given time, so 4G or 5G networks can run simultaneously.

In one of the “Core” machines, there are 4 VM machines:

- 1 VM for the complete 4G Core, using the OpenAir-CN version develop branch.
- 1 VM for the complete 5G Core, using OpenAir-CN version v1.4.0.
- 1 VM for the exposition of RAN network slicing capabilities in 4G networks, using the FlexRAN version²⁴ developed.

²⁴ See: <https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/developer/topic-technology/edge-5g/tools/flexran.html>

- 1 VM for the exposition of RAN network slicing capabilities in 5G networks, using FlexRIC version 8534bccb²⁵.

When both LXC 5G RAN and KVM VM 5G Core are up and running, the completely operational 5G infrastructures will become available. At UWS premises, 4G and 5G Cores have prepopulated cryptographic information inside 5 SIM cards.

Figure 28: UWS infrastructure topology

The infrastructure is complemented by 2 UEs:

- 1 UE - OPPO RENO6 5G
- 1 UE - OnePLUT 8T

These mobile phones are connected to the Ettus USRP B210²⁶ when the RAN and CORE are connected and receive configuration to access any machine deployed as a VM in the infrastructure and Internet access.

²⁵ Also see, for example: <https://gitlab.eurecom.fr/mosaic5g/flexric>

²⁶ See: <https://www.ettus.com/all-products/ub210-kit/>

Figure 29: OpenAirInterface architecture deployed in UWS testbed

2.4.2 Compute, Storage and Networking Capabilities

All the machines are Dell T5810 with 12 cores (24 hyper-threaded), 2 TBB HDD, and 32GB RAM.

Five physical machines act as Compute (Nova) to deploy services within the infrastructure. Four of the five are installed using KVM as a hypervisor, whereas the other uses LXC.

The LXC physical machine is logically assigned to Zone “Edge 1.” Another physical machine with KVM is logically assigned to Zone “Edge 2”, and the other 3 machines are logically assigned to Zone “Core”. These assignments are configurable and can be changed if necessary. Two machines in the “Core” and one in the “Edge 2” are completely free and available for service deployment.

The LXC Compute machine is also connected to an Ettus USRP B210 Software Defined Network Radio Interface using USB. To allow the USB passthrough to be exposed to the LXC containers, a live detection and attachment of the USB have been built and deployed on our premises.

All the machines are connected using a 10 GB network as a data plane. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows a photo of the data centre in UWS premises dedicated to 6G-PATH experimentation facilities.

Figure 30: Computer, Storage and Network Capabilities at UWS Testbed

2.4.3 Virtualisation, Management and Orchestration

There are 3 physical management machines: “Controller”, “David”, and “Goliath”. A controller is a physical machine with only a virtualisation layer based on KVM and is used to create multiple virtual machines for

management purposes. Controller, thus, has 4 different virtual machines for management: “MaaS Controller”, “Juju Controller”, “6G-Path Controller”, and “6G-Path Advance Services”. The role of each one in the management and orchestration of the UWS testbed is the following:

- “MaaS Controller VM” has installed inside Ubuntu Metal-as-a-Service 2.9.3 and its MaaS client as well. It allows the management of the physical infrastructure to perform.
- “Juju Controller VM” has been installed inside an Ubuntu Juju Controller 2.9.43 machine. It allows us to manage the infrastructure services.
- “6G-Path Advance Services” will be installed inside all the components required to provide the advanced features tested and available in 6G-Path.
- The “6G-Path Controller” will be installed inside all the components required to provide the 6G-Path dashboard and access to the testbed.
- “David” and “Goliah” have all the services required for the operational management of a completely functional, highly high-available advanced OpenStack infrastructure (Wallaby 5.6.0 release²⁷) with advanced capabilities such as OVN networking²⁸, Vault for encryption of the management plane and high-availability with RabbitMQ²⁹ and MySQL quorums³⁰. Each of these services is deployed in LXC containers to achieve a fully micro-service deployment architecture where each LXC container is isolated and has only one functionality.

Figure 31: Topological Monitoring Capabilities @UWS testbed

2.4.4 Monitoring Capabilities

Our customised monitoring platform has been deployed, allowing us to gather metrics related to devices, network ports, services, and network flows along most of the infrastructure. They rely on Nagios probes, Linux kernel probes, and other standard probes such as NetFlow and sFlow³¹. The monitor is also extended to discover

²⁷ See, *inter-alia*: <https://docs.openstack.org/releasenotes/python-openstackclient/>

²⁸ See: <https://www.ovn.org/en/>

²⁹ See: <https://www.rabbitmq.com/>

³⁰ See: <https://dev.mysql.com/doc/mysql-cluster-manager/8.4/en/mcm-quorum.html>

³¹ See, *for example*: <https://www.cisco.com/c/en/us/td/docs/iosxr/cisco8000/netflow/configuration/b-netflow-configuration-ios-xr-8000/netflow-sflow-key-concepts.pdf>

network topologies that will later be used as a feed for the use case UC-EDU-2. Figure 31 shows a screenshot of the discovered topology within the testbed.

2.4.5 Security Capabilities

The whole test is located behind a VPN access that allows controlled access to the testbed and deals with authorisation and protection mechanisms to enable authorised remote access while blocking any attempt to get into the infrastructure from non-authorized users. In summary, the testbed is not publicly exposed, and instead, access is performed via VPN services.

Figure 32: APIs exposed by the UWS testbed

2.4.6 Configuration and Control APIs

The testbed exposes 3 different APIs: Metal-as-a-Service, OpenStack, and Juju.

- **Metal-as-a-Service** allows the configuration of new bare metal computers to be customised for particular needs in the data centres, thus allowing the dynamic re-usage of physical resources.
- **Juju** allows the automatic installation of services, which are first packaged in a standardised way and then automatically deployed using this API on demand.
- **OpenStack** allows the complete management of virtual infrastructure and cloud resources, providing both software-defined networks and virtual networks that can be managed accordingly.

2.4.7 Description of the Network Scenarios

The current deployment of the testbed is limited to an indoor deployment, with mobility limited to the areas of the building covered by the testbed. The testbed is fully available for experimentation, possibly providing complete in-house testing. We have Linux systems, and we work with Android phones. Under this scenario, we are flexible in allocating what is provided for experimentation. Currently, there is a limitation on the quality of access to the Internet; thus, any remote use case will be impacted by the “best-effort” quality of service provided by the current Internet service provider available on premises.

The details of the configurations available are described below.

Table 22: Reference scenario @UWS testbed

Band	N41
Mode	TDD
Bandwidth	20 MHz
MIMO-layer	1 layer
DL MIMO mode	1x1
Beams	Single beam
Subcarrier-spacing	30 kHz
Uplink/Downlink slot ratio	1/8
Location	University Campus

Table 23: Reference scenario @UWS testbed

Band	N78
Mode	TDD
Bandwidth	20 MHz
MIMO-layer	1 layer
DL MIMO mode	1x1
Beams	Single beam
Subcarrier-spacing	30 kHz
Uplink/Downlink slot ratio	1/8
Location	University Campus

2.4.8 Mapping of experimentation requirements from the internal use cases to the testbed features

This testbed will host the UC-EDU-2 use case. In this case, the own testbed is required to install agents along the complete set of physical and virtual nodes to allow the generation and publication of the complete testbed's topology. The holographic devices will use this information to render the complete topology for teaching purposes. Holographic devices require high bandwidth and low latency to interact smoothly with the testbed's digital twin. The testbed's advanced slice management capabilities will achieve this. The complete topology will be rendered in the cloud and then delivered to the headset to achieve acceptable rendering and response times. We will push the limits of connectivity vs. computation to investigate the best trade-off.

2.5 FOKUS testbed

This section summarises the status of FOKUS tested by October 2024 (M10), as depicted in Figure 33. The components, configurations, planned extensions, and how the platform fulfils the use case requirements will be described in detail in the following subsections.

Figure 33: 6G-PATH Initial Release @ FOKUS testbed

2.5.1 5G Infrastructure @ FOKUS testbed

The Fraunhofer FOKUS Testbed is a multiple vendors testbed for SA (Standalone) 5G Core-RAN (Radio Access Network) integration and testing. The testbed demonstrates various proof-of-concept scenarios, including various RAN vendors, multiple user equipment, and different backhauls. The architecture of the Fraunhofer FOKUS testbed is illustrated in Figure 34.

Figure 34: 5G Fraunhofer FOKUS Testbed Infrastructure

The Fraunhofer FOKUS testbed provides the Open5GCore [18] software toolkit that is developed by Fraunhofer FOKUS. The software core network is built for easy reconfigurability using different configuration file sets. It allows testing different scenarios and use cases by switching between different configuration sets. The Open5GCore comprises multiple Network Functions (NFs) developed per the 3GPP specified specifications. It

includes the components: AMF, AUSF, UDM, NRF, SMF, PCF, UPF, NSSF, N3IWF, SCP, LMF, GMLC and NEF network function.

Figure 35: Open5GCore 5G SA Core Network

The Open5GCore core network from Figure 35 supports multiple features from the 3GPP specifications. The Fraunhofer FOKUS testbed runs one or more features for different tests/projects. These features are described in Table 24.

Table 24: Open5GCore features and their description

Feature	Description
Basic 5G Core (AMF, AUSF, UDM, NRF, SMF, UPF)	5G Core setup with a minimal set of components to provide Authentication and Internet access to the users.
Slicing	Support slices on all protocol layers and NAS-based rerouted slicing at the N2 interface .
Application Function	Support for 3 rd Party API control via NEF for Traffic Influence API.
Non-3GPP Access	Authentication and handover of UEs between 3GPP and non-3GPP access technologies.
Roaming	Support for Home-routed roaming for authentication and data path via SCP.
Location Services	UE and gNB provide support for LPP and NRPPa-based location services.

The FOKUS testbed is equipped with 5G base stations from multiple vendors. The installations are part of different ongoing projects and integrations for RAN-Core compatibility. The base stations integrated with the Open5GCore are ADAPTIT, Amarisoft, ASOCS Cyrus, Ericsson, Huawei, NodeH, Nokia and Sercom (the base station providers requested an alphabetic order list) as well as open source: Open Air Interface and SRS 5G. Additionally, Open5GCore was tested against the Keysight IxLoad tool³², which is the testing tool used by most of the commercial core network developers and the Defensics fuzzifier³³ for security tests.

The 5G base stations in the testbed operate in the 3.7 - 3.8 GHz campus network band. Coverage is provided in the test laboratory, outdoors around the FOKUS premises with the radios installed on the building’s rooftop, and

³² See: <https://www.keysight.com/us/en/products/network-test/protocol-load-test/ixload.html>

³³ See: <https://www.blackduck.com/fuzz-testing.html>

indoors in the parking garage. The indoor and outdoor radios allow different proof-of-concepts in large and small coverage zones.

The Open5GCore is integrated and tested with off-the-shelf phones like Apple, Google Pixel, Huawei, Nokia, Samsung, and many CPEs (Quectel, Huawei, etc.). Additional ones are now in testing. All the UEs and CPEs in the lab are accessible remotely, enabling more tests without being present in the lab.

Figure 36: Fraunhofer FOKUS testbed

The FOKUS testbed has multiple backhaul options for testing backhaul use-cases. There is a long-haul fibre connection with terminations in FOKUS to simulate a large distance backhaul with a long cable, and a satellite backhaul for NTN use cases is also available. The FOKUS testbed provides LEO connectivity via the Starlink network. In addition to the non-exclusive Starlink device already available on the testbed, an additional Starlink Terminal was acquired, which will significantly improve the availability of the Satellite link during the experiments. To utilise Starlink connections inside the testbed, a VPN tunnel must connect back into the testbed from the SpaceX HUB offloading point. Currently, the management of the VPN tunnels is shared with the general-purpose VPN access used for experimenters.

Figure 37: NTN Integration @ FOKUS

The NTN integration, as depicted in Figure 37, was tested by using the Starlink system to connect a remote nomadic node to a 5G Core running in the FOKUS Testbed. The Nomadic node consisted of an edge server, a Nokia BBU, together with a power supply and Starlink, in a mobile rack mounted in a protective carry-on case. Depending on the mobile node's location, UEs could handover between 5G cells connected directly to the 5GCore or via the NTN backhaul link.

2.5.2 Compute, Storage and Network Capabilities

The Fraunhofer FOKUS testbed comprises six Cisco UCSB-B200-M5 servers³⁴ with 192 CPU cores (403GHz), 1.5TB RAM and 10TB Storage capacity, as shown in Figure 38. The servers run a VMware ESXI cluster with multiple tenants for each project. Each project has its network layer provided by Cisco switches and routers. The testbed uses 100Gb fibre backhaul connectivity between the servers. In addition, similar connectivity extends to the 5G RANs deployed in the environment.

Figure 38: Infrastructure Capabilities

The testbed also includes a satellite backhaul connection via Starlink dish.

2.5.3 Virtualisation, Management and Orchestration

The Open5GCore is a software and vendor-independent toolkit, hence not restricted by the hardware capabilities. The testbed is used for multiple projects in parallel; hence, the deployment type changes based on the requirements. The Open5GCore network functions are deployed as system services without any virtualisation to get maximum performance from the hardware. However, in some instances, the core orchestration is done via Kubernetes or Virtual Machines. The Kubernetes server is set up locally for a given project; the testbed is not using a common Kubernetes server. The Open5GCore is currently in the process of integration with the Open Nebula platform for deployment purposes.

The testbed supports management for the Open5GCore network and the UEs (access only). The 5G core network components have APIs exposed that allow managing them over the network for every component deployed in the testbed. These are mainly JSON-RPC APIs with a webpage embedded in them. Device Farmer software³⁵ is used to access the UEs remotely. It is open-source software that enables working on the testbed without being physically present.

2.5.4 Monitoring Capabilities

The FOKUS testbed is not exporting metrics for the complete testbed, as the infrastructure is shared between different projects. Each deployed core network exports its metrics individually. The Open5GCore exports

³⁴ See: <https://www.cisco.com/c/en/us/support/servers-unified-computing/ucs-b200-m5-blade-server/model.html>

³⁵ See: <https://github.com/DeviceFarmer>

memory and measurement data via Prometheus API for every 5G network function. A Prometheus server collects these metrics and visualises them on a Grafana dashboard.

The Open5GCore components natively export memory statistics that show memory usage over time. These statistics are available for the different sets of memory pools used in the component architecture. In addition to memory statistics, the UPF exports user plane statistics. These include the packets received, forwarded, dropped, and buffered. These statistics are collected for every interface of the UPF. This data enables the calculation of the UPF's per-interface throughput in Grafana.

```

14:14:31>AMF>
139997923493632/2421529 14:14:31 NOTICE:command:list_matching_commands():707> amf.ng.print_nodes
139997923493632/2421529 14:14:31 NOTICE:command:list_matching_commands():707> amf.ue.kill
139997923493632/2421529 14:14:31 NOTICE:command:list_matching_commands():707> amf.ue.print_contexts
139997923493632/2421529 14:14:31 NOTICE:command:list_matching_commands():707> amf.ue.send_paging
139997923493632/2421529 14:14:31 NOTICE:command:list_matching_commands():707> exit
139997923493632/2421529 14:14:31 NOTICE:command:list_matching_commands():707> get_log_cfg
139997923493632/2421529 14:14:31 NOTICE:command:list_matching_commands():707> help
139997923493632/2421529 14:14:31 NOTICE:command:list_matching_commands():707> history
139997923493632/2421529 14:14:31 NOTICE:command:list_matching_commands():707> http_client.curl_verbose.disable
139997923493632/2421529 14:14:31 NOTICE:command:list_matching_commands():707> http_client.curl_verbose.enable
139997923493632/2421529 14:14:31 NOTICE:command:list_matching_commands():707> httpd_h2o.logger
139997923493632/2421529 14:14:31 NOTICE:command:list_matching_commands():707> httpd_h2o.registered_paths
139997923493632/2421529 14:14:31 NOTICE:command:list_matching_commands():707> list_exec_unit
139997923493632/2421529 14:14:31 NOTICE:command:list_matching_commands():707> mem_stat
139997923493632/2421529 14:14:31 NOTICE:command:list_matching_commands():707> nrf_client.nf_table_print
139997923493632/2421529 14:14:31 NOTICE:command:list_matching_commands():707> set_log_level
139997923493632/2421529 14:14:31 NOTICE:command:list_matching_commands():707> version
14:17:02>AMF>amf.ng.print_nodes
139997923493632/2421529 14:17:02 INFO:command:execute_module_cmd():215> cmd reply:
amf_comm_reply
----- [ngran_node_ht] -----
Number of entries: 1 empty slots: 31 out of 32
Hash 23,          entries: 1
      gNB
-----
gNB ID:          1001
RAN Node Name:   gnb1
NG-C addr:       192.168.12.50:38412
SCTP Assoc ID:   76
-----
----- [ngran_node_ht] end -----
14:19:39>AMF>

```

Figure 39: Open5GCore monitoring command-line interface

Along with Prometheus APIs, the core provides monitoring via the command line. The Open5GCore platform has its command line built-in, as seen in Figure 39. This allows executing commands for debugging and checking states on multiple components. The core components include print commands for displaying monitoring and debugging data.

Figure 40: Configuration and control APIs @FOKUS testbed

2.5.5 Security Capabilities

A dedicated VPN server that utilises the Wireguard protocol [19] to provide secure tunnels into the testbed network provides access to the FOKUS testbed. For each project, the VPN server provides an isolated instance that separates the traffic between different testbeds of different projects. The VPN server is hosted as a Linux-based virtual machine on the VMware part of the testbed. By using Linux, the VPN is very flexible and can be adapted if an experimenter needs non-standard settings or different VPN protocols. The VPN server also integrates external testbeds or components from Open Callers into the FOKUS testbed infrastructure.

The diagram in Figure 41 depicts how a nomadic node and/or a third-party service could be securely connected to the core network deployed at the FOKUS testbed over public infrastructure like the Internet.

Figure 41: Secure access to the FOKUS testbed

Figure 42: UE Management GUI

2.5.6 Configuration and Control APIs

Figure 40 shows the APIs exposed in the FOKUS testbed. These APIs are used for data collection and state information gathering of the components. The APIs for monitoring tools are exposed via TAP plugins, which will be integrated with ELCM to control the phones. In infrastructure management APIs, these are the APIs exposed by components to export monitoring data via the Prometheus endpoint defined in every 5G Core component network function. Along with monitoring, the network functions expose access and debug APIs. The availability of a given type of API depends on the type of network function and the designed purpose.

In advance experimentation features, the APIs for Security-as-a-Service (SECaaS) and Policy Enforcer are already described in the deliverable D2.1³⁶. The slice manager will be developed in the next phase; hence, the API description is not feasible. The 5G core components in Open5GCore expose APIs for managing and controlling the subscribers/network functions. The APIs are categorised into two parts: APIs standardised by 3GPP and APIs outside 3GPP specifications, as shown in Figure 42.

³⁶ 6G-PATH project: Deliverable 2.1: *Platform architecture and verticals – Initial*. Available at: <https://6gpath.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/6G-PATH-D2.1-Platform-architecture-and-verticals-v1.0.pdf>

2.5.6.1 5G Components API

The 5G Core components offer APIs for controlling user access management and data path handling. The API exposed by NEF triggers the traffic influence mechanism.

The following example shows a curl command triggering an HTTP POST request to create a subscription via a traffic influence API in NEF.

```
curl -X POST -H "Content-Type: application/json" -d @- "http://192.168.11.20:8080/3gpp-traffic-influence/v1/af1/subscriptions"
```

Along with the create command, the NEF also exposes a delete API for deleting the subscription.

2.5.6.2 Management API

The management of the core components is primarily done by the command line interface provided by every core component, as shown in Figure 39. The core also exposes a JSON-RPC API for exporting the logs and executing the supported commands in the components via a web browser. The webpage needed is integrated into the source code; hence, no separate front end is necessary. Figure 42 and Figure 43 highlight the embedded webpages for handling software UE and 5G core network functions.

Figure 43: Open5Gcore component GUI

2.5.7 Description of the Network Scenarios

The reference scenario provided for experimentation is described in Table 25:

Table 25: FOKUS band n78 configuration

Band	n78
Mode	TDD
Bandwidth	100 MHz
MIMO-layer	4 layers
DL MIMO mode	4x4

Beams	Single beam
Subcarrier-spacing	30 kHz
Uplink/Downlink slot ratio	2/7
Location Testbed	Fokus Lab

2.5.8 Mapping of experimentation requirements from the internal use cases to the testbed features

Use case vertical Health, which includes 3D Hydrogel Patch and Elderly Monitoring use cases, will be supported by the FOKUS testbed. Both use cases require deploying a full or partial 5G Core network on the use case locations along with the appropriate base station connectivity. The services are provided over a 5G private network. Public infrastructure will be used as a backhaul between the use case location (edge) and the central location (FOKUS Testbed located at Fraunhofer FOKUS premises). This includes public MNVOs and LEO satellite connectivity to ensure high availability and resilience due to the critical nature of the use cases.

The functional and performance requirements of the UC-Health-1 and UE-Health-2 are given in Table 26 and Table 277.

Table 26: Functional requirements UC-Health-1 and UC-Health-2

FR	Title	Description
FR1	5G Private Network Connectivity	Deployment of the 5G private networks at the edge locations
FR2	Backhaul	Reliable connectivity between central and edge nodes
FR3	Integration of edge devices	E2E functionality of the use cases

Table 27: Performance requirements UC-Health1 and UC-Health2

PR	Title	Description
PR1	Availability	>99.99%
PR2	Reliability	>99.99%
PR3	Low backhaul delay	<10ms

2.6 KAU testbed

The Communication Advanced Research Laboratory Wireless Testbed (CARL-W) is located on the Campus of Karlstad University, Karlstad, Sweden, and is part of the Northstar Testbed. CARL-W is managed by the Computer Science Department at Karlstad University in cooperation with Telia (operator) and Ericsson (HW supplier). The communication infrastructure, built on standard fibre and 10GbE, integrates a communication network with radio terminals (4G, 5G, WiFi and Starlink). The testbed connects several user equipment and technologies like mobile phones, IoT devices, and virtualisation and containerization solutions (Kubernetes/docker).

Figure 44 summarises the KAU testbed's status by October 2024 (M10). In the following subsections, we will further detail testbed components, configurations, and planned extensions and describe how the testbed fulfils the use case requirements.

Figure 44: 6G-PATH Initial Release @KAU testbed

2.6.1 5G Infrastructure @KAU testbed

CARL-W is equipped with a commercial indoor 5G system (Ericsson Radio Dot), with four radio dots deployed in Karlstad University’s engineering building and one in the nearby Innovation Park building, which hosts industry clusters and startups.

The testbed provides 5G NSA and SA connectivity using 100 MHz in Band n78, and Low Latency capabilities (less than 5 ms one-way delay) through so-called Local BreakOut (LBO) for local User Plane Function (UPF) deployment. The performance has been validated with a series of 5G devices and hardware components, such as Cradlepoint R1900³⁷, Mikrotik³⁸, Huawei CPE, Quectel RM500³⁹, and 5G SA-enabled mobile phones (e.g., CrossCal devices). The setup suits capacity-intensive services, low latency applications, and other demanding use cases (VR/AR, smart industry, etc.).

The layout of the 5G section of CARL-W is depicted in Figure 45. Figure 46 shows some of the areas at Karlstad University covered by the 5G section of the testbed. These include a large experimental space where various use cases can be staged.

³⁷ See: <https://cradlepoint.com/product/endpoints/r1900-series/>

³⁸ See: <https://mikrotik.com/>

³⁹ See: <https://www.quectel.com/product/5g-rm500u-series/>

Figure 45: The 5G section of the CARL-W testbed at Karlstad University

Figure 46: Areas at Karlstad University covered by the 5G section of CARL-W

2.6.2 Compute, Storage and Networking Capabilities

The backhaul infrastructure is based on standard Single/Multi-mode optical Fibres and 100/10 GbE technologies.

As mentioned, the 5G radio dots are placed in two buildings on the Karlstad University Campus. The radio dots are directly connected to a Local Radio Unit (LRU) in each building, and both LRUs form a single cell served by a baseband unit covering 2 floors of the buildings. The physical infrastructure of the access network comprises one-to-one fibre links aggregated by a switch supporting 10 GbE connection. The main uplink (to the Internet) is established with 2x10 GbE ports running over the University's 2x100 GbE Internet uplink. Starlink and other communication types (e.g., WiFi) are realised as separate networks and gateways connected into the testbed network, giving it five possible Internet connections (Wired, 5G, 4G, Starlink and WiFi). The testbed also facilitates the automated deployment of applications using containerisation technologies, i.e., microservices. The team managing the CARL-W testbed self-hosts the server infrastructure/data centre side. The data centre consists of multiple servers managed by VMware vCenter (8) connected by Cisco 10 GbE switches deploying all virtual machines and network functions running in the cloud, such as Kubernetes and docker swarm. To complement the data centre, we also have bare-metal installations where time-critical workloads are deployed and edge nodes/UEs (Raspberry Pi, Nvidia Jetson, and various COTS mobile phones).

2.6.3 Virtualisation, Management and Orchestration

Kubernetes performs the testbed orchestration. CARL-W utilises specific descriptors to describe the service requirements (e.g., network technology, service type): testbed worker nodes are divided by the type of network technology they use, but the testbed is technology agnostic in the sense that it does not mandate a particular connection technology. However, all devices that should be part of the network orchestration need to support Wireguard, Docker/Kubernetes and have a routable IP address (i.e., be able to reach the Internet).

2.6.4 Monitoring Capabilities

The testbed has both infrastructure and service monitoring capabilities:

- We monitor the infrastructure by collecting data from different network technology endpoints (e.g., 5G, Starlink) and the status of the compute infrastructure components, e.g., CPU and Memory load. The monitoring of the computing infrastructure is based on the DESK monitoring framework [20] and utilizes a set of open-source components.
- Application and service performance monitoring evaluates network resources, service status, etc. Automated performance monitoring includes continuous monitoring of capacity and latency performance. Some eBPF-based tools for fine-grained latency and inter-packet delay monitoring are also available [21], [22]. These tools are currently started manually when fine-grained monitoring is required.

The monitoring information is collected in an InfluxDB database⁴⁰. Part of it is also made available live through a Grafana web interface (see <https://5g.carl.kau.se/live>). Figure 47 displays an example of part of the live visualisation.

Figure 47: Example of visualisation of monitored data in CARL-W

2.6.5 Security Capabilities

No special security capabilities are available. Access to nodes within the KAU infrastructure is available through VPN access.

⁴⁰ See: <https://www.influxdata.com/>

2.6.6 Configuration and Control APIs

CARL-W offers connectivity over preconfigured network slices that can be selected by the experimenter. Currently, two slices are configured: one standard eMBB-like slice and one high-priority slice. The slices can be reconfigured, but only on a slow time scale.

Figure 48: Exposed APIs @ KAU testbed

The testbed also offers RAN support for low-latency, low-loss scalable throughput (L4S) signalling. The MAC scheduler handles L4S traffic separately. L4S is controlled by the configuration of the applications/end hosts. For TCP-based applications, the use of L4S can be controlled through the selection of the OS configuration of the end hosts. Connectivity over Starlink, WiFi and 4G is also available to the experimenters. Moreover, the infrastructure allows external (third-party) sensors, network devices, or services to extend the testbed. The demanding requirements of external devices/services to join the testbed are: (i) to be able to run wireguard; (ii) to operate as a Docker/Kubernetes host, and; (iii) to have an Internet connection.

2.6.7 Description of the Network Scenarios

The network allows experiments to be freely setup using one or more of the available network technologies, e.g. 5G and Starlink measurements, 5G - edge (wired) or any other combination of network technologies available in the testbed. However, one current limitation is that we cannot do experiments where both the server and client are on the same network technology and orchestrated by the testbed; when one of the endpoints is external, it is possible to use the same technology experiments. The current testbed deployment is limited to indoors, with mobility limited to the areas of the engineering building covered by the testbed. However, an outdoor coverage extension is underway and will be available by the end of 2024. This will allow experimentation with handovers between indoors and outdoors and limited outdoor mobility scenarios.

Table 28: KAU indoor/outdoor band configurations

Band	n78 (indoor, outdoor), n28 (outdoor)
Mode	TDD
Bandwidth	100 MHz
MIMO-layer	4 layers

DL MIMO mode	4x4
Beams	4 n78 outdoor, 1 n78 indoor, 1 n28 outdoor
Subcarrier-spacing	30 kHz n78 and 15 kHz n28
Uplink/Downlink slot ratio	n78 TDD == DDDSU (10:2:2)
Location Testbed	KaU Lab

2.6.8 Mapping of experimentation requirements from the internal use cases to the testbed features

Within 6G-PATH, CARL-W will support the XR health education use case, which focuses on enhancing the training of ambulance nurses. Practical training is an essential part of such education and is typically acquired in two ways: working in simulated environments with manikins and participating in real medical scenarios. We focus here on the simulated scenario with manikins, the main target for the 6G-PATH experimentation.

Manikins simulate human anatomy and physiology, allowing learners to extend their knowledge by experiencing lifelike situations. When training on manikins, the teacher is usually situated in the room next door and provides the voice response of the manikin and also controls specific reactions in response to the actions taken by the students, such as the change in breathing when the students move the head of the manikin to clear its airways. The more authentic the scenarios simulated with the manikins are, the better the learning experience. Within 6G-PATH, it is proposed to move the manikin from its fixed classroom to locations that create a more authentic medical scenario, such as inside an ambulance, allowing the manikin to be remotely controlled and also allowing paramedic nursing students virtually to take part in remote simulated acute/ambulance scenarios in an immersive manner.

Realising such a scenario involves several components. The manikin and cameras are placed at the simulated medical site to collect high-quality video and microphones/speakers for audio input/output. The manikin's control takes place at a remote site. Furthermore, rendering devices at a (possibly distributed) remote training site, such as audio-video peripherals (e.g., monitors, or head-mounted displays), will be used by the remote students to take part in the scenario in an immersive way.

The medical site will be connected over the CARL-W 5G network, where the manikin control and audio will be sent over the high-priority slice, and the video will flow over the default slice. The use of L4S to control latency will also be evaluated. Computing nodes for the generation of the XR content that integrate the multimodal inputs collected at the medical site and any further non-real-time information will be deployed within the CARL-W server infrastructure, as will the application server(s) that will provide access to the XR content by the students at the training site.

A main challenge in realizing the use case will be integrating all the hardware and software components needed in the testbed. While some parts can be easily automated, the manikin and its associated control will likely require manual intervention to initiate experimentation.

2.7 ALB/IT testbed

The Aveiro testbed (IT/ALB) is in Aveiro and encompasses the Aveiro Tech City Living Lab (ATCLL), which is spread over the city and on the site of the University of Aveiro, and the B5G infrastructure setup at the ALB campus.

Figure 49: 6G-PATH Initial Release @ALB/IT testbed

2.7.1 5G Infrastructure @ALB/IT testbed

The ATCLL comprises many Internet of Things (IoT) devices with communication, sensing, and computing capabilities. The communication infrastructure, built on fibre and millimetre-wave (mmWave) links, integrates a communication network with radio terminals (WiFi, ITS-G5, C-V2X, 5G and LoRaWAN), multiprotocol, spread throughout 44 connected points of access in the city. Additionally, public transportation has also been equipped with communication and sensing units. All these points combine and interconnect sensors, such as mobility (radars, LiDARs, and video cameras) and environmental sensors. Combining edge computing and cloud management to deploy the services and manage the platform and a data platform to gather and process the data, the living lab supports a wide range of services and applications: IoT, intelligent transport systems (ITSs) and assisted driving, environmental monitoring, emergency and safety, among others.

The ALB testbed joins different open-source software aiming to provide an infrastructure capable of supporting real-life applications requiring advanced network and service capabilities. It includes user equipment, radio access technology, core network entities and management and orchestration functionalities. Furthermore, it encompasses a data management and analytics platform that allows data from heterogeneous sources to be gathered and presented in an integrated format.

The Aveiro testbed’s architecture is shown in **Error! Reference source not found..** It can support demonstration scenarios and interact with external models to set up and deploy specific test cases.

2.7.2 Compute, Storage and Networking Capabilities

The ATCLL backhaul infrastructure is based on Single-Mode optical Fibre (SMF) link technology (G.652), spanning a length of 16 Km. It interconnects the 44 edge nodes covering the urban area of Aveiro, deployed on Smart Lamp Posts or wall boxes on building facades. The physical infrastructure of the access network comprises one-to-one fibre links aggregated by a switch supporting 10 GbE connections and SDN functionality through Open vSwitch (OVS) [26] or P4. The uplink to the core is established with 40 GbE ports. Other types of backhaul

communication include millimetre-wave and satellite communications. The mesh network composing the backhaul also includes 5 millimetre-wave antennas linking Smart Lamp Posts directly for SDN experiments (in the University of Aveiro Campus, and 3 nodes in the city centre). The Non-Terrestrial Network (NTN) domain of the infrastructure relates to 2 Starlink business antennas on the rooftop of the IT building, giving the network three Internet connections. SDN support enables network control through software, utilising open-source controllers like Ryu and ONOS and control plane protocols OpenFlow and P4 Runtime. These SDN controllers are deployed in the core of the network and dynamically react to possible changes in demand and network conditions. Moreover, network algorithms and Machine Learning (ML) techniques are incorporated to monitor and act within the network. For instance, in the vehicular network (V2X), algorithms within the SDN controller facilitate Internet connectivity and handovers in the mobile nodes. This platform also facilitates the automated deployment of applications using containerisation technologies, microservices, and Kubernetes for end-to-end orchestration support. Additionally, various services in different nodes can be personalised through dynamic allocation and orchestration based on Quality of Service (QoS) and dynamic slicing management. Time Sensitive Network (TSN) functions are also supported on the network’s backhaul. To assist critical services with bounded-latency requirements or with required bandwidths, the network is synchronised to a nano-second precision, and it is possible to configure the network switches with different types of shapers (e.g., TAS, CBS). The infrastructure is complemented at the core by a network and data processing centre. The data centre consists of multiple servers managed by Proxmox VE⁴¹, deploying all virtual machines with services, data platform, apps, 5G core (Open5GS), and network functions running in the cloud, such as Kubernetes, Open Source MANO (OSM), ChirpStack, among others.

Figure 50: Overall ATCLL 5G and Edge Architecture

There are common entities set up under both IT and ALB sites, namely:

RAN: The RAN infrastructure is comprised of various solutions, including OpenAirInterface (OAI) and srsRAN, open-source solutions deployed in Ettus Research USRPs, and CableFree 4G/5G Small Cell n46/n78 indoor/outdoor, commercial solutions. Both open-source solutions are O-RAN compliant gNB with CU/DU split and interconnect with RAN Intelligent Controllers (RICs) for RAN monitoring. For RIC solutions, ONF’s SD-RAN

⁴¹ See, for example: <https://www.proxmox.com/en/proxmox-virtual-environment/overview>

and FlexRIC were attested (soon ORAN SC RIC) and used for metric collection and data processing through ML strategies.

5G Control Plane: The Open5GS Core is a set of software components and network functions that interact with each other. Our Open5GS SA Core has the following functions: NRF, SCP, SEPP AMF, SMF, UPF, AUSF, UDM, UDR, PCF, NSSF and BSF. This Core uses a Service Based Architecture (SBA). The NRF is set up to register control plane functions, and the NRF then assists them in finding the other essential functions. Mobility and connection management is handled by the AMF. The UDM, AUSF, and UDR generate SIM authentication vectors and maintain subscriber profiles. The SMF is in charge of session management. The roaming security architecture includes SEPP, PCF is utilised for charging and enforcing subscriber policies, and the NSSF allows for network slice selection. The SCP allows for indirect communication. The 5G SA core user plane is substantially more straightforward, with only one function. The UPF transports user data packets between the external WAN and the gNB. It is also connected to the SMF.

This core supports local breakout roaming with the aid of the SEPP module. It enables the Mobile Network Operator (MNO) to break out internet sessions into the Home Network, providing inbound roamers with the ability to order data, which is provided directly by the visited network. It also supports VoNR by adding an NF from the 4G Core, the HSS, the main subscriber database used within the IP Multimedia Subsystem (IMS), and the Kamailio SIP server⁴² to provide public telephony service.

In collaboration with OneSource, their implementation of the NEF can be integrated with Open5GS for network interaction either directly through the NEF or from an external AF. The tested services are Traffic Influence and AF Session with Required QoS (“TS 129 522 - V17.6.0”⁴³), as Open5GS currently supports these.

5G Data/User Plane: Open5GS allows for Control User Plane Separation (CUPS), which disaggregates the User Plane Function (UPF) from the control plane, enabling MEC and reducing backhaul distances. The Packet Forwarding Control Protocol (PFCP) implemented in Open5GS (N4 interface) follows 3GPP standardisation, thus integrating with external UPF implementations, such as UPG-VPP and eUPF. The first project is a user plane gateway implemented as an out-of-tree plugin of VPP with DPDK [27] for packet processing acceleration. Which converts the UPF into a programmable router, providing an API for external runtime configuration and VPP network metric collection. The second project uses xBPF for packet processing and can be configured for various 5G architectures. It also provides an API for user plane monitoring.

UEs: The user equipment possibilities include SIM cards, modems, CPEs, and smartphones.

- The **SIM cards** used are the programmable sysmoSIM-SJA2 and sysmoSIM-SJS1 SIM cards⁴⁴ and CableFree’s non-programmable SIMs. The programmable SIM cards can be programmed with the OMNIKEY 3121 smart card reader⁴⁵ and pySIM⁴⁶.
- **5G modems** from Quectel, SIMCom and SierraWireless are available with devkits and are managed by ModemManager.
- Two indoor **CPEs** operating in bands 46 and 78.
- And finally, a wide variety of **5G smartphones**, such as Google Pixel, Xiaomi, OPPO and Samsung, for compatibility with all types of deployed RAN.

MEC: The MEC system deployment was considered to address smart-city scenarios with edge nodes spread out across various locations with a 5G edge-enabled deployment to address the users’ mobility and the edge

⁴² See: <https://www.kamailio.org/w/>

⁴³ See: <https://cdn.standards.iteh.ai/samples/66256/7b38764abfb24b62a9736b1aa506f087/ETSI-TS-129-522-V17-6-0-2022-07-.pdf>

⁴⁴ See: <https://www.sysmocom.de/products/sim/sysmousim/index.html>

⁴⁵ See: <https://www.hidglobal.com/products/omnikey-3121>

⁴⁶ See: <https://doc.pysim.org/tutorial.html>

environment's dynamic nature while improving the Quality of Service (QoS). This was accomplished with extensions to base edge architecture through the appropriate plug-ins, custom resources and components to address the dynamic nature of this environment and the mobility of the users.

The 5G edge-enabled deployment logic associated each edge node with a gNB and an edge UPF. The gNBs serve as a connection point providing radio access to the end-users using 5G-radio technology, while the role of the edge UPF within the context of this architecture is to route the user traffic to its associated nearest edge node. This deployment ensures that user traffic is routed to the nearest server and additional hops can be avoided, contributing to an optimised QoS in the service consumption.

ALB, supported by IT infrastructure, will have access to many smart city data for different purposes. It provides traffic information that can be used for different types of applications. Applying the information to achieve the desired behaviour in real-time is possible. These data and other city-related details are managed at Live!Urban platform⁴⁷. The Live!Urban concentrates on a single operational control point the functionalities needed to visualise, analyse, and act on urban control systems and infrastructures. Live!Urban allows the integration of different services and technologies belonging to different functional domains (verticals) seamlessly and transparently, using specific APIs to interact with the different systems. Live!Urban resorts to the functionalities provided by data management platforms to ingest, process, store and share city information, reinforcing the capacity to manage and control city functional domains. The solution supports different data systems and devices from different manufacturers, regardless of the radio access technology (e.g., NB-IoT, LoRa, 3G, 4G, 5G).

Figure 51: 5G Edge-enabled deployment

⁴⁷ See: https://www.alticelabs.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/BR_LiveUrban_ALB_EN.pdf

Figure 52: Live!Urban Platform

2.7.3 Virtualisation, Management and Orchestration

The platform is implemented across several VMs that perform different functions to achieve coherent slices of defined network services.

The Aveiro testbed supports descriptors for adapting the service implementations. Additionally, load-balancing mechanisms can forward the requests of each service for the best replica, considering the network and host state. These elements with the above functionalities are available in this group of repositories <https://github.com/orgs/nap-it/teams/6g-path/repositories>. The server infrastructure side is also self-provided. The infrastructure is complemented at the core by a network and data processing centre. The datacentre consists of multiple servers managed by Proxmox VE⁴⁸, deploying all virtual machines with services, data platforms, apps, 5G core (Open5GS), SRSRan and network functions running in the cloud (Kubernetes). Notice that this infrastructure supports a cloud continuum with a cloud, edge and device continuum. Beyond the server infrastructure in the core, we run the microservices and the detection and actuation algorithms in the edge infrastructure previously described (NVIDIA Jetson Orin and Jetson Xavier⁴⁹ with a powerful GPU for graphic-intensive processing) and the access nodes in the vehicles (OBUs, DCUs).

The edge orchestration mechanisms were deployed using Kubernetes with a couple of extensions and plugins to the base architecture because, by default, the Kubernetes platform is unable to respond to the dynamic demands of smart-city services, especially in a vehicular environment where the users are in constant movement since it was developed for the cloud. Such extensions include:

- **FogService:** A new type of resource called FogService, whose definition enables the possibility to define the deployment of services optimized for the edge environment by providing capabilities such as defining instantiation locations, number of replicas, and service-specific metrics that can be used to assess the status of the replicas and instantiation based on node's capabilities.
- **Custom Load Balancer:** By default, the Kubernetes load-balancing algorithm ensures that each replica receives the same number of network requests as the others. In edge-road environments, such logic is inadequate. As such, a custom Load Balancer was developed to influence the probability of each replica receiving a request, considering service-specific metrics and the network latency reflected on the cluster.
- **Scheduling Plugins:** The addition of new plugins extended the Kubernetes scheduling process to augment its capabilities, allowing for a more flexible and complete scheduling process that considers factors such as the priority of the services, the applications that are already in execution, the dependencies between services, service performance, etc.

⁴⁸ See: <https://www.proxmox.com/en/proxmox-virtual-environment/get-started>

⁴⁹ See, among others: <https://forums.developer.nvidia.com/t/performance-of-orin-vs-xavier/304129>

- **Mobility Management mechanisms:** New components were developed to gather data from external sources and proactively influence service performance and distribution across the edge platform. Such data includes 5G and edge computing platform status, city congestion status, user mobility information, etc.

The following are development/deployment tools and software:

- **Docker or ContainerD:** A software platform for building, testing, and deploying applications that packages software into standardised units called containers. Containers offer a lightweight and isolated environment that contains all the dependencies, libraries, and tools needed to run an application.
- **Kubernetes:** An open-source orchestration platform for the management of containerised applications. It provides features such as storage orchestration, self-healing container capabilities, horizontal scaling, and batch execution, designed to allow for the addition of extensions without changing the source code.
- **Prometheus** is an open-source monitoring and alerting system. It collects and stores its metrics as time-series data. Its main features include a flexible query language to leverage a multidimensional data model, an intermediary gateway for pushing time-series data, no reliance on distributed storage, and data gathering via a pull model over Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP).
- **MongoDB:** Open-source distributed database system that stores data in flexible Javascript Object Notation (JSON) format, with the capability for Ad hoc queries, indexing and real-time aggregation to provide powerful ways to access and analyse the data stored in the database. It also offers high availability and horizontal scaling capabilities.
- **Proxmox** is an open-source platform for enterprise virtualisation. Its built-in web interface allows intuitive management of Virtual Machines (VMs) and containers. The platform also offers software-defined storage and networking and high-availability clustering.
- **Ansible:** An open-source automation engine that automates provisioning, configuration management, application deployment, orchestration and other processes. It uses simple human-readable scripts to automate tasks and eliminates repetition with a low maintenance overhead by avoiding additional software installation.
- **Grafana:** An open-source monitoring platform that allows users to query, visualise, and configure alerts for the metrics independently of their storage location and enables the creation of dynamic and reusable dashboards.
- **Portainer:** A lightweight container management UI that allows you to manage different Docker environments, hosts, and swarms easily. It enables seamless operation in diverse environments, including datacentre, public cloud, network edge and Industrial IoT devices. All of the testbed's edge nodes are connected to Portainer, which makes it possible to access the dockerised services running in each node.
- **Openslice:** Allows Vertical clients to browse service specifications, onboard service descriptions, VNFs, and their management. In particular, it integrates the following components:
 - **Services Portal:** Provides a portal to allow users to access services and service providers to design services.
 - **Products Portal:** Provides an NFV portal for users to manage NFVs and onboard them to a target MANO orchestrator.
 - **Testing Portal:** Allows testing users to build associated tests for a deployable service.
 - **Resources Portal:** Manages and shows the available resources in the underlying infrastructure.

2.7.4 Monitoring Capabilities

The ELK stack⁵⁰ is attached to VMs or Kubernetes containers in a sidecar configuration to obtain protocol monitoring and security practices. Thus, a pocket IDS is ready to perform monitoring and security-related jobs.

Figure 53: Monitoring Framework

IDS is constituted by 5 different CNFs:

- Suricata will capture IP packets, and for that, it needs privileged access to the network interface to achieve a promiscuous mode. It will store all captured IP packets in logs (eve.json) inside a directory mounted by the second CNF.
- Filebeat, which picks up the logs and send them to the following CNF - logstash.
- Logstash will be the focus of alarm detection. Logstash is an open-source tool for collecting, parsing, and resending logs for other uses. The inputs can be defined as the sources for parsing, in this case, a stream from Filebeat. The method for parsing the input logs is defined in a way that detects the alarms in filters. We also define three outputs from log stash: access to elastic search and a directory in flat files that a light HTTP server will read. This HTTP server will, upon pooling from Prometheus, send a warning to the monitor, stating which IP will be under attack so the platform can act and finish the threat.
- Elasticsearch is a document database that stores the alarms obtained on log stash for future use and supports persistency for Kibana the following CNF.
- Kibana is the CNF responsible for the visualisation of the alarm packets. It picks those alarms from the elastic search DB. It may provide a deep alarm analysis and multiple graphic visualisations in selected contexts.

Figure 54: Data visualiser

⁵⁰ See: <https://aws.amazon.com/what-is/elk-stack/>

When opening the Kibana interface in the browser using the address `http://localhost:5601/`, one can go to Analytics>Discover, choose the index that we created in Logstash and select the data to visualise using the graphs that Kibana offers, and we can add to a dashboard.

To complement this previous information, all sorts of parameters from SRSRan, CableFree or OPEN5GS are dedicated to characterising the streams and relations established inside running services. The 5G systems are heterogeneous and present a high diversity of equipment and technologies. As such, monitoring the status of this system requires dealing with various information formats and different ways to access this information. Monitoring 5G systems in the Aveiro infrastructure was divided into two sources (Figure 54):

- 5G Core monitoring: A couple of Open5GS core network functions include an HTTP server that exposes metrics regarding the status of those network functions. With an additional Prometheus server, these metrics can be scraped and stored in a time-series database to be later accessed for analytics, complex processing, or visualised with other software applications (e.g., Grafana).
- RAN monitoring: Aveiro’s cellular infrastructure includes two technologies implementing the gNBs: CableFree and srsRAN. Both solutions expose a couple of metrics regarding their performance, but they are gathered differently. As such, the solution for this issue consisted of creating two metrics servers responsible for collecting the metrics from both gNB technologies and then publishing them in the data platform using the appropriate data format. Both servers are implemented as docker containers with a simple Python script to fetch the metrics.

A Kafka Cluster allows other entities to subscribe to a RAN-related topic and get real-time updates about the platform’s status. Moreover, to persist the RAN data, a Mongo Database cluster is used so that other services can take advantage of a larger data set to perform some complex analysis of historical data. This was accomplished with a Kafka Sink connector that persists the data of a specific Kafka topic in the Mongo Cluster. Core metrics are already aggregated in a dedicated Prometheus server and do not persist in the Aveiro data platform. Applications that wish to access such information access the Prometheus server endpoints directly.

Aveiro testbed provides detailed metrics in the 5G infrastructure from RAN to Core.

2.7.5 Security Capabilities

The platform will have remote access via OpenVPN, Tailscale [30], and Portainer [31] (for container management), which are inherently protected by the security features of each access technology. Cybersecurity threat detection will be addressed on demand based on the ELK stack. Each time a possible vulnerability is identified, a VM or Kubernetes container will be followed by an ELK stack connected to Prometheus. Several decisions will be made depending on the specific policy to address intrusion detection and prevention and DOS situations.

Figure 55: 5G RAN and Core metrics collection

Figure 56: APIs exposed by ALB/IT testbed

2.7.6 Configuration and Control APIs

The Aveiro Testbed presents the following configuration and control API:

- **ELK:** Access in real-time to what is happening, in terms of target IP-based protocols, to service nodes considered in danger of non-authorized access. This may involve access to a history of events located on ElasticSearch, visualisation of real-time events on Kibana, or reception of important events from Logstash.

- **RAN and 5G Core metrics:** A couple of Open5GS core network functions include an HTTP server that exposes metrics regarding the status of those network functions. With an additional Prometheus server, these metrics can be scraped and stored in a time-series database to be later accessed for analytics, complex processing, or visualised with other software applications (e.g., Grafana). RAN also exposes metrics regarding their performance, and this data is persisted in Kafka. Complementary to passing this information to the ELCM 6G-PATH framework, all the data from RAN and 5G Core is stored in MongoDB, too.
- **OSM:** The services manager will accept actions usually associated with MANO events, such as creating and deleting network microservices. These actions will be provided externally to create a microservice with the designated VNFs and the deletion by the provided service ID.
- **Kubernetes Mobility Manager:** New components are added to Kubernetes to gather data from external sources and proactively influence service performance and distribution across the edge platform. Such data includes 5G and edge computing platform status, city congestion status, user mobility information, etc. It can be configured and tuned through API according to the use case.
- **SliceManager:** It will provide slices of the designated microservices available to the service manager and their deletion when requested.
- **Kubernetes FogService:** A new type of resource for Kubernetes called FogService, whose definition enables the possibility to define the deployment of services optimised for the edge environment by providing capabilities such as defining instantiation locations, number of replicas and service-specific metrics that can be used to assess the status of the replicas and instantiation based on node's capabilities.

2.7.7 Description of the Network Scenarios

This section includes the tables that describe the configurations available in the ALB/IT testbed.

Table 29: ALB-srsRAN@ALB Campus

Band	n78
Mode	TDD
Bandwidth	20 MHz
MIMO-layer	MIMO: 2T2R, 2 layer DL, 1 layer UL
DL MIMO mode	2x2
Beams	Single beam
Subcarrier-spacing	30 kHz
Uplink/Downlink slot ratio	2/7
LocationTestbed	Altice Labs Campus

Table 30: IT—srsRAN 20 MHz MIMO

Band	n78
Mode	TDD
Bandwidth	20 MHz
MIMO-layer	2 antennas DL, 2 antennas UL
DL MIMO mode	2x2
Beams	single beam
Subcarrier-spacing	30 kHz
Uplink/Downlink slot ratio	gain 80/45
LocationTestbed	IT – University Campus and City

Table 31: IT—srsRAN 40 MHz

Band	n78
Mode	TDD
Bandwidth	40 MHz

MIMO-layer	2 antennas DL, 2 antennas UL
DL MIMO mode	2x2
Beams	single beam
Subcarrier-spacing	30 kHz
Uplink/Downlink slot ratio	gain 80/45
LocationTestbed	IT – University Campus and City

Table 32: IT—Cablefree

Band	n78
Mode	TDD
Bandwidth	50 MHz
MIMO-layer	2 antennas DL, 2 antennas UL
DL MIMO mode	2x2
Beams	single beam
Subcarrier-spacing	30 kHz
Uplink/Downlink slot ratio	gain 90/65
LocationTestbed	IT – University Campus and City

2.7.8 Mapping of experimentation requirements from the internal use cases to the testbed features

The ALB/IT testbed will support UC-CITIES-1 – Connected and Sensing City and UC-CITIES-3 – Security Coordination.

The UC-CITIES-1 use case involves vehicles (some of them autonomous) of various types, people, and environmental and mobility sensors (e.g., video cameras, radars, and lidars), all connected and transmitting real-time information between the sensors, roads, and infrastructure. This overall scenario will be used to explore the following sub-scenarios:

- High-distribution video on the move
- Coordinated and controlled mobility
- Enhanced city services with AI
- Digital twin, merging real and simulated data

To support this use case, most of the capabilities of the testbed will be utilised, including:

- Multi-technology communications (5G, ITS-G5, etc.)
- Sensors and edge computing
- Mobility metadata and network utilisation metrics
- Resource allocation and service migration with edge computing
- Autonomous vehicles and connected vehicles and people
- UEs and wearable devices on pedestrians
- B5G network (RAT, Core, Slice Manager)
- Mobility and environment sensors on bikes and buses through IoT
- Data Management Platform

The UC-CITIES-3 use case focuses on emergency services communication involving the dispatch of emergency response teams (police, firefighters, military forces, etc.) to different locations. The goal is to investigate the use of various communication technologies to assess the performance and efficiency of security coordination in a given situation. We aim to improve this coordination through secure communications, refined geolocation, and control tools, including situational awareness dashboards and real-time crime mapping information.

To support this use case, utilising multiple communication technologies available in the city and Altice Labs testbed is essential. This includes various private 5G infrastructure (SDR, commercial gNBs, and open-source core) and complementary networks (ITS-G5, Wi-Fi, etc.). Obtaining mobility and network KPIs is also crucial to better predict and anticipate responses and to develop a reliable network architecture with reduced latency.

3 6G-PATH framework components (Initial release)

3.1 Initial release

The 6G-PATH framework components included in the initial release are highlighted in red in Figure 57. The Experiment Life-Cycle Manager (ELCM) Portal [17] served as the primary user interface for editing the configuration and controlling the execution of the experiments. It provides a web-based interface where users can define the experiments. The ELCM is responsible for orchestrating the entire lifecycle of 5G experiments. Acting as a backend engine, it coordinates the execution and management of the experiments from start to finish. These two components are integrated with InfluxDB to support the persistent storage of the measurements collected during the experiment and Grafana to visualise the data. Additionally, a list of monitoring agents was included in the initial release to support the execution of throughput and latency tests and validate the performance of the platforms.

Figure 577: 6G-PATH framework initial release

3.1.1 ELCM

The ELCM is the component that allows the execution and orchestration of experiments in the different 6G-PATH testbeds. It will enable the execution of concurrent experiments (allowing the isolation of the testbeds’ resources). Experiments are defined as a set of test cases, which, in turn, are described as the set of actions that must be performed to generate the desired results.

These actions (for instance, executing a command, sending a request to an API, retrieving some measurements, and delegating to another orchestration solution, among others) correspond to one of the tasks implemented in the ELCM. The ELCM contains pre-defined tasks for many everyday actions that a testbed owner may require to execute a test case. In contrast, new tasks can be easily implemented by following simple guidelines.

Once a test case has been defined, it can be exposed to experimenters via the ELCM Portal. At the same time, advanced users and testbed owners can use the ELCM APIs to control the execution of experiments directly.

The following sub-sections detail the tasks that have been developed during the initial phase of the 6G-PATH project.

3.1.1.1 Helm deploy task

The *Run.HelmDeploy* task is responsible for developing applications in a Kubernetes cluster using Helm Charts [2]. This allows experimenters to manage application versions and utilise advanced Helm functionalities such as rollback or release deletion. The task runs in the cluster specified by the *kubeconfig* file where the ELCM resides.

Configuration parameters

- **Action:** Defines the action to be performed on the chart. Available options are:
 - Deploy: Deploy the Helm chart to the cluster.
 - Delete: Delete the specified Helm release.
 - Rollback: Rolls back the deployment to a previous version of the chart defined for the release name.
- **Namespace:** The Kubernetes namespace where the action will be performed. If this parameter is omitted, the cluster's default namespace is used.
- **ReleaseName:** The name assigned to the Helm release. This name must be unique within the namespace. It is used to manage the deployment's lifecycle.
- **HelmChartPath:** The path to the Helm chart to be deployed. It specifies the chart's location in the filesystem from which Helm will pick it up.

An example of a test case in YAML format can be seen below:

```
Version: 2
Name: Helm Agent
Sequence:
- Order: 1
  Task: Run.HelmDeploy
  Config:
    Parameters: []
    HelmChartPath: "<path/to/helm/chart>"
    Action: "Deploy"
    ReleaseName: "nginx-v1"
    Namespace: "uma"
    CWD: '.'
Standard: True
Distributed: False
Dashboard: {}
```

3.1.1.2 Prometheus task

The task allows queries to be made to a Prometheus [3] server to extract metric data and store it in InfluxDB. This process facilitates monitoring the status of resources and services during experiment execution.

Configuration Parameters:

- ExecutionId (required): Unique identifier for the execution.
- URL (required): URL of the Prometheus server.
- Port (required): Port number for Prometheus server connection.
- QueriesRange (optional): List of range queries to execute.
- QueriesCustom (optional): List of custom (instant) queries to execute.
- Measurement (required): InfluxDB measurement name where data will be sent.
- Stop (required): Signal to stop data retrieval.
- Step (required): Step interval for range queries.
- Account (required): Flag indicating when user and password is used (True or False).
- Certificates (optional): Path to SSL/TLS certificate files, needed if encryption is used.
- Encryption (required): Flag indicating whether SSL/TLS encryption is used (True or False).

Encryption:

This task uses encryption to secure the connection:

- **TLS/SSL:** If enabled, the connection to Prometheus is secured using TLS/SSL. The configuration includes:
 - **Certificate File** (client-cert.pem): Authenticates the client to Prometheus.
 - **Private Key File** (client-key.pem): Establishes the client's identity.
 - **CA File** (ca.pem): Verifies the Prometheus server's certificate.

YAML Configuration Example:

```
Version: 2
Name: PROMETHEUS
Sequence:
  - Order: 1
    Task: Run.PrometheusToInflux
    Config:
      ExecutionId: "@{ExecutionId}"
      Url: "prometheus.example.com"
      Port: "9090"
      QueriesRange:
        - "query_range_1"
        - "query_range_2"
      QuieriesCustom:
        - "custom_query_1"
        - "custom_query_2"
      Measurement: "my_measurement"
      Stop: "stop_flag"
      Step: "1s"
      Account: True
      Certificates: "/path/to/certificates/" # Optional, if encryption is used
      Encryption: True # Set to True if TLS/SSL is used, False otherwise
```

Note: It is necessary to use a stop task (StopTask) to halt the execution of the Run.PrometheusToInflux task. This ensures that the task terminates properly and stops retrieving data from Prometheus.

3.1.1.3 Kafka task

This task is responsible for consuming data from a Kafka topic and transferring it to an InfluxDB database. The goal is to ensure that the data generated during the execution of experiments is stored for later analysis.

Configuration Parameters:

- ExecutionId (required): Unique identifier for the execution.
- IP (required): IP address of the Kafka broker.
- Port (required): Port number for Kafka broker connection.
- Topic (required): Kafka topic to consume messages from.
- Measurement (required): InfluxDB measurement name where data will be sent.
- Stop (required): Signal to stop message consumption.
- Account (required): Flag indicating when user and password is used (True or False).
- GroupID (optional): Kafka consumer group ID, used to manage offsets and group consumption.
- Certificates (optional): Path to SSL/TLS certificate files, needed if encryption is used.
- Encryption (required): Flag indicating whether SSL/TLS encryption is used (True or False).

Encryption:

This task uses encryption to secure the connection:

- **TLS/SSL:** If enabled, the connection to Kafka is secured using TLS/SSL. The configuration includes:
 - **Certificate File** (client-cert-signed.pem): Authenticates the client to the Kafka broker.
 - **Private Key File** (client-key.pem): Establishes the client's identity.
 - **CA File** (ca-cert.pem): Verifies the Kafka broker's certificate.

YAML Configuration Example:

```
Version: 2
Name: KAFKA
Sequence:
  - Order: 1
    Task: Run.KafkaConsumerToInflux
    Config:
      ExecutionId: "@{ExecutionId}"
      Ip: "X.X.X.X"
      Port: "XXXX"
      Topic: "my_topic"
      Measurement: "my_measurement"
      Stop: "stop_flag"
      Account: True
      GroupId: "my_group"      # Optional
      Certificates: "/path/to/certificates/" # Optional, if encryption is used
      Encryption: True        # Set to True if TLS/SSL is used, False otherwise
```

Note: It is necessary to use a stop task (StopTask) to halt the execution of the Run.KafkaConsumerToInflux task. This ensures that the task terminates properly and stops retrieving data from Kafka.

3.1.1.4 MQTT task

This task manages the subscription to an MQTT [4] topic, data reception, and data storage in InfluxDB. It integrates devices operating under the MQTT protocol, such as IoT sensors, into the experimental environment.

Configuration Parameters:

- ExecutionID (required): Unique identifier for the execution.
- Broker (required): Address of the MQTT broker.
- Port (required): Port number for MQTT broker connection.
- Account (required): Flag indicating when user and password is used (True or False).
- Topic (required): MQTT topic to subscribe to.
- Stop (required): Signal to stop message processing.
- Measurement (required): InfluxDB measurement name where data will be sent.
- Certificates (optional): Path to SSL/TLS certificate files, needed if encryption is used.
- Encryption (required): Flag indicating whether SSL/TLS encryption is used (True or False).

Encryption:

This task uses encryption to secure the MQTT connection:

- **TLS/SSL:** If enabled, the connection to the MQTT broker is secured using TLS/SSL. The configuration includes:
 - **Certificate File** (client-cert.pem): Authenticates the client to the MQTT broker.
 - **Private Key File** (client-key.pem): Establishes the client's identity.
 - **CA File** (ca.pem): Verifies the MQTT broker's certificate.

YAML Configuration Example:

```

Version: 2
Name: MQTT
Sequence:
  - Order: 1
    Task: Run.MqttToInflux
    Config:
      ExecutionId: "@{ExecutionId}"
      Broker: "mqtt_broker_address"
      Port: "8885"
      Account: True
      Topic: "my_topic"
      Stop: "stop_flag"
      Measurement: "my_measurement"
      Certificates: "/path/to/certificates/" # Optional, if encryption is used
      Encryption: True # Set to True if TLS/SSL is used, False otherwise

```

Note: It is necessary to use a stop task (StopTask) to halt the execution of the Run.MqttToInflux task. This ensures that the task terminates properly and stops retrieving data from MQTT.

3.1.1.5 SSH task (based on credentials)

The CliSsh task establishes an SSH connection to a remote server, executes a specified command, and logs the output or any errors encountered during execution. It supports multiple types of private key authentication, including SA⁵¹, ECDSA⁵², and Ed25519⁵³.

Configuration Parameters:

- Hostname (required): The hostname or IP address of the SSH server.
- Port (optional): The SSH port (default is 22).
- Username (required): The username for the SSH connection.
- Certificate (required): Path to the private key file used for authentication (supports RSA, ECDSA, and Ed25519).
- Command (required): The command to execute on the remote server.

YAML Configuration Example

```

Version: 2
Name: CLI_SSH
Sequence:
  - Order: 1
    Task: Run.CliSsh
    Config:
      Hostname: "192.168.1.100" # IP address or hostname of the SSH server
      Port: 22 # SSH port (default is 22)
      Username: "user" # Username for the SSH connection
      Certificate: "/path/to/private_key" # Path to the private key for authentication
      Command: "ifconfig" # Command to execute on the remote server

```

3.1.2 ELCM Portal

The ELCM Portal provides a unified interface for experimenters to make use of the experimentation capabilities of the testbeds: For experimenters, this interface removes the complexity of creating test cases, limiting the customisation to a pre-defined set of configurable parameters. For platform owners, it separates external users and the testbed capabilities, restricting access to the actual components.

⁵¹ For further information see, *inter-alia*: [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/RSA_\(cryptosystem\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/RSA_(cryptosystem))

⁵² Also see, *for example*: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Elliptic_Curve_Digital_Signature_Algorithm

⁵³ See, *among others*: <https://cryptobook.nakov.com/digital-signatures/eddsa-and-ed25519>

Internally, the ELCM Portal makes use of the ELCM APIs for retrieving information about the available test cases and for requesting the execution of experiments, while on the front-end it:

- Implements user registration and authentication, including access control for specific test cases.
- Provides a graphical user interface for the definition of experiments.
- Gives access to execution logs and results and to pre-configured Grafana dashboards for visualisation.

The ELCM Portal was updated during the initial development phase to provide improved customisation capabilities for each experimentation platform. The Portal now allows custom images and descriptions, allowing every 6G-PATH testbed to provide a front-end adapted to its corporate image. Additionally, the code of the ELCM Portal has been simplified, removing unused dependencies.

The screenshot shows the 'CREATE EXPERIMENT' page in the ELCM Portal. At the top, there are navigation links for 'Home', 'Create Experiment', and 'Info'. The main heading is 'CREATE EXPERIMENT'. Below this, there are two input fields: 'Name' (a text box) and 'Type' (a dropdown menu currently showing 'Standard'). Underneath, there are three sections: 'Test Cases' with a list of checkboxes for TESTCASE1, TESTCASE2, PING, ALLTEST, KAFKA, PROMETHEUS, TELEGRAF, and MQTT; 'UEs' with checkboxes for UE_S0_IN, UE_S0_OUT, and UE_local; and 'Scenarios' with a dropdown menu currently showing 'Scenario1'.

Figure 58: ELCM Portal

3.1.3 Common monitoring tools

For this initial Release, the monitoring agents described in D2.1 and developed as part of the 5GENESIS project⁵⁴ have been included without modifications. The agents support Windows and Android; for the final release, Linux support will be included, and the control plugins will be updated.

3.1.4 InfluxDB and Grafana

The ELCM can work with InfluxDB database versions **V1 and V2**. InfluxDB is a time-series database designed to handle large volumes of data generated at high speed. Its query languages, InfluxQL or Flux, enable complex analysis and time-based queries. It has two main versions: InfluxDB V1, which focuses on influxQL, and V2, which introduces Flux along with other features like buckets and an enhanced API. Using an InfluxDB database instance with the ELCM is enough to indicate its credentials in the *config.yml* file. An example of configuration for InfluxDB V1 and V2 is presented below.

```
#InfluxDB v1 configuration file
InfluxDb:
  Enabled: True
```

⁵⁴ See: <https://5genesis.eu/>

```
Host: "<InfluxDB host>"
Port: "<InfluxDB port>"
User: "<InfluxDB user>"
Password: "<InfluxDB password>"
Database: "<database name>"
```

```
#InfluxDB v2 configuration file
InfluxDb:
  Enabled: True
  Host: "<InfluxDB host>"
  Port: "<InfluxDB port>"
  Database: "<database or bucket name>"
  Token: "<access token>"
  Org: "<organization name>"
```

Once the database is configured, data can be injected into any ELCM task. Below is an example of a possible test case that used the task `CsvToInflux`.

```
InfluxDbTest:
  - Order: 5
    Task: Run.CsvToInflux
    Config:
      ExecutionId: "@{ExecutionId}"
      CSV: "<csv_path>" # Replace with the location of the file
      Measurement: <measurement name>
      Delimiter: < delimiter character i.e.: ;>
    Standard: True
    Distributed: False
    Dashboard: {}
```

Grafana is an open-source platform for monitoring and visualising data from various sources. It allows users to create dynamic dashboards and graphs to track metrics over time. Grafana supports multiple data sources like InfluxDB and Prometheus, offering a wide range of plugins for extended functionality. If a Grafana instance is set up and properly configured, the ELCM can automatically generate a dashboard to display “key” raw results produced during the execution of an experiment. The test case definition must contain a collection of Grafana panel definitions to utilise this feature. For each experiment run, the panels from all selected test cases will be combined into a single dashboard. An example of a dashboard definition with one panel is shown below.

```
Dashboard:
  - Name: "Slice Deployment Time"
    Measurement: Slice_Creation_Time
    Field: Slice_Deployment_Time
    Unit: "s"
    Type: Singlestat
    Percentage: False
    Size: [8, 8]
    Position: [0, 0]
    Gauge: True
    Color: ["#299c46", "rgba(237, 129, 40, 0.89)", "#d44a3a"]
    Thresholds: [0, 15, 25, 30]
```

For this release, the ELCM has been updated to work with the V1 and V2 versions of the InfluxDB data source. This allows the creation of dashboards capable of receiving data from both versions of InfluxDB.

The ELCM can also generate additional dashboards to capture values generated by the Open TAP [5] tool. To use this functionality, an additional result listener (AutoGraph) must be enabled in the TAP tool. This result listener does not require any extra configuration, and once enabled, the auto-generation of panels will work for any subsequently executed experiment.

Figure 59: Influx Data Pipeline Web interface

3.1.5 Influx Data Pipeline

The Influx Data [29] Pipeline is designed to write CSV files into an InfluxDB V2+ database. This tool can inject measurements into the database when it is impossible to do so during the experiment or when the monitoring tools don't provide an automatic interface for retrieving data. In this situation, the data can be manually exported to CSV files and injected into the InfluxDB for later correlation, with the rest of the measurements aggregated into the database.

It provides a web interface where users can input the required metadata for CSV uploads, with an alternative option for direct usage through POST requests. The Influx Data Pipeline supports writing one or more CSV files to the selected bucket (database) with the specified metadata. An image of the interface is shown below.

The tool can be used both through the web interface (see Figure 59) and by REST calls with JSON files with metadata. Below is an example of well-formed JSON, and in Annex 1 shows a user manual for the tool's installation and use.

4 Advanced features (initial release)

This subsection describes the advanced experimentation features provided in the initial release. The advanced features have been classified into five topics. For each topic, different implementations come from different partners, as can be seen in Figure 60 below.

Figure 60: Advanced experimentation features (Initial Release)

4.1 Security as a Service

4.1.1 CAPIF

The Common API Framework (CAPIF) is designed to provide a standardised and secure way for network functions and services in 5G networks to expose and consume APIs. This section describes how third parties can use this service to access the APIs exposed via CAPIF safely. The process of how an invoker (or client) obtains an authorisation token from the CAPIF services and uses it to access APIs is explained below and depicted in **Error! Reference source not found.** It is a seamless but secure system that simplifies API interactions while maintaining strict authorisation standards.

Step 1: Token Request from CAPIF

Before accessing any API, the client must secure a valid token through registration, authentication, and authorisation.

Client Registration

The first step in this process is registration. Here, the client introduces itself to the CAPIF system, acquiring credentials like a client ID and a client secret. These identifiers serve as the foundation for secure interactions between the client and CAPIF.

Authentication

Once registered, the client uses its credentials to authenticate with CAPIF. This critical step confirms the client's identity and may employ robust methods like mutual TLS (Transport Layer Security) or other CAPIF-supported mechanisms to establish trust.

Token Request Submission

With authentication complete, the client formally requests an access token from CAPIF's Authorization Function. The request typically includes:

- The grant type specifies the type of access flow (e.g., client credentials).
- The client ID and secret are proof of identity.
- The scope detailing the APIs or permissions being requested.

Validation

Upon receiving the token request, CAPIF rigorously validates the client’s credentials and ensures that the requested scopes align with the client’s permissions. This provides the integrity of the request and prevents unauthorised access.

Token Generation

If the client passes the validation checks, CAPIF generates a token—often a JWT (JSON Web Token). This token encapsulates key information:

- Client identity for tracking.
- Scopes or permissions that define what the client can access.
- Expiration time to enforce temporal validity and reduce risk.

Token Delivery

The generated token is then securely delivered to the client and ready for API interactions.

Step 2: Accessing APIs with the Token

The token is the client’s key to accessing APIs hosted by AEFs, but the journey doesn’t end there. The AEF must verify and validate the token before processing any requests.

Making the API Request

The client initiates an API call, embedding the token as a bearer token in the request’s Authorization header. This header informs the AEF of the client’s authorisation status.

Secure Transmission

All communication between the client and the AEF occurs over HTTPS, ensuring that the token and other sensitive data are protected in transit.

Token Validation

When the AEF receives the request, it performs a series of checks to validate the token:

- Signature Verification: For JWT tokens, the AEF uses CAPIF’s public key to ensure that CAPIF issued the token and that it remains unaltered.
- Expiration Check: The AEF verifies that the token is still within its valid time frame.
- Scope and Permission Validation: This ensures the token authorises the requested API or resource.

Access Decision

If it is valid, the AEF will process the API request and return a response to the client. If it is invalid, the request is denied, and an appropriate HTTP status code (e.g., 401 Unauthorized or 403 Forbidden) is returned, along with an error message.

Step 3: Logging and Auditing

To maintain accountability and monitor security breaches, CAPIF and the AEF log all key events, such as authentication attempts, token generation, and API access. These logs are essential for auditing, troubleshooting, and detecting anomalies in the system.

This structured and technical process ensures that CAPIF delivers a secure, scalable, and efficient framework for client interactions with APIs, balancing strict authentication protocols with practical usability.

Figure 61: Workflow of the usage of CAPIF

4.1.2 WireGuard connectivity

The security as a service component is developed to provide secure connectivity between central and edge nodes. This connectivity is limited to edge nodes and third-party Integrators to have a secure communication channel between the core and an external application function over public infrastructure.

The network tunnel protocol WireGuard provides security for communication. The server is deployed in Fraunhofer FOKUS premises. For security reasons, this component is internal and will not be exposed to external services via APIs. Fraunhofer FOKUS personnel must generate access configurations for edge nodes or on-demand third-party integration.

4.2 Slice Manager

4.2.1 Slice manager (UMA)

The slice manager in the UMA testbed is based on Nokia's NaC (Network as a Code) solution. The APIs exposed by NaC are used for managing the slices and were previously introduced in D2.1. This section provides example code for accessing specific APIs related to IMSI management, network slices, QoS profiles, and radio status.

NaC server-client architecture leverages RESTful APIs to allow seamless integration of network capabilities into applications. This architecture focuses on enabling applications to interact with network resources and features as needed, abstracting away the complexities of network management.

The NaC server is a centralised provider that exposes network capabilities through REST APIs. These APIs allow clients to interact with various network functionalities, such as Quality of Service (QoS) and network slicing (see **Error! Reference source not found.**).

On the client side, applications connect to the NaC server using a Python-based NaC library or SDK, which provides ready-to-use methods for making API calls. This library simplifies client interactions, enabling developers to request network features without understanding the underlying network infrastructure.

Clients initiate requests (e.g., adjusting network QoS, checking device location) through API calls. The SDK abstracts away HTTP handling, so developers call functions within their application code. The server processes the request and returns a response in JSON or XML format.

Figure 62: NaC client-server communication workflow

4.2.1.1 Slices and IMSIs management

The `slices_get` API in the Network API Catalog (NAC) is an endpoint for retrieving information about network slices. Network slicing is a key feature in 5G networks, allowing operators to partition network resources into virtual slices tailored for specific use cases (e.g., enhanced mobile broadband, IoT, low-latency applications). Below is an example of a script that returns the list of the created slices in the site AdaByron.

```
from __future__ import print_function
from nac_client import NacApi
from pprint import pprint

# Create instance of the NaC API class:
api = NacApi()

print(f'\n##### List of created Slices for site "AdaByron":\n')
try:
    pprint(api.Slices_get(location='malaga_uma', site='AdaByron'))
except Exception as e:
    print(e)
```

4.2.1.2 QoS profiles management

Quality of Service (QoS) profiles in the context of the Network API Catalog (NAC) are key tools for managing and ensuring network performance for various applications and services. These profiles define network services' performance characteristics and requirements, allowing clients and network functions to allocate resources tailored to specific use cases dynamically.

```
from __future__ import print_function
from nac_client import NacApi
from pprint import pprint

# Create instance of the NaC API class:
api = NacApi()

print(f'\n##### Get QoS profiles configured for the user:\n')
```

```
try:
    pprint(api.Qos_profiles())
except Exception as e:
    print(e)
```

It can also be specified an IMSI and retrieve the slice sessions assigned to this slice in the 5G core and the QoS profiles assigned in NaC to it:

```
from __future__ import print_function
from nac_client import NacApi
from pprint import pprint

# Create instance of the NaC API class:
api = NacApi()
imsi = '001010000000700'
print(f'IMSI: {imsi}\n')
try:
    pprint(api.Qos_profiles(imsi))
except Exception as e:
    print(e)
```

It is also possible to deregister an IMSI from a slice:

```
from __future__ import print_function
from nac_client import NacApi
from pprint import pprint
import sys

# Create instance of the NaC API class:
api = NacApi()
imsi = '001010000000700'
print(f'\n##### Deregister IMSI from slice:\n')
try:
    pprint(api.Imsis_deregister(imsi))
except Exception as e:
    print(e)
```

4.2.1.3 Radio status

The Radio_status endpoint in the Nokia Network API Catalog (NaC) is designed to provide information and monitor the radio access network's operational status. This endpoint allows clients to query various aspects of the radio network's performance and health, facilitating efficient network management and decision-making for applications relying on robust connectivity. In particular, cell id, band, mode, plmn, radio_ip, site, status, time and type can be retrieved by using the following Radio_status endpoint:

```
from __future__ import print_function
from nac_client import NacApi
from pprint import pprint

# Create instance of the NaC API class:
api = NacApi()

print(f'\n##### Radio status:\n')
try:
    pprint(api.Radio_status())
except Exception as e:
    print(e)
```

4.2.2 Slice Manager (UWS)

The advanced functionalities of End-to-End Slice Management are currently being developed at UWS and are planned to be available in the second round of open calls.

The Slice Manager (SM) delivers end-to-end (E2E) network slicing in multi-tenant, multi-domain 5G/6G environments. Its goal is to create an adaptable, interoperable, and flexible network-slicing framework to support the complex requirements of 6G deployments. To achieve this, the SM must provide a robust slicing control solution capable of managing the diverse array of programmable network devices and technologies within the data plane.

Figure 63: Slice Manager Architecture Overview

The initial prototype of the SM includes three core components, as depicted in **Error! Reference source not found.**, each of which plays a crucial role in enabling the system's overall functionality:

1. **SM North-Bound Interface (NBI) - API REST:** The Slice Manager offers a North-Bound Interface (NBI) through a REST API, utilising JSON messages for communication. This interface allows upper-layer components like orchestration platforms to interact with the SM seamlessly.
2. **E2E Slice Engine:** The E2E Slice Engine manages network slices actively enforced in the data plane. It provides slicing capabilities to upper layers by utilising detailed network topology data supplied by the Topology Inventory Agent. This agent gives the SM a comprehensive view of the network's structure, enabling efficient decision-making regarding where slices should be applied for an optimal E2E deployment. Once the Slice Engine determines the appropriate slice placement, it sends a "technology-agnostic slice definition" to specify actions like creating, deleting, or associating network flows with specific slices.
3. **Slice Controller Agent (SCA):** The SCA serves as the South-Bound Interface for the Slice Manager, acting as a distributed component deployed across the infrastructure nodes that may host network slices. The SCA provides programmability for the various underlying technologies and network interfaces in the data plane, particularly those related to the lifecycle management of network slices. It abstracts the complexity of the data plane, presenting a unified API to upper layers while utilising specific slicing enablers. The SCA translates

the “technology-agnostic slice definition” messages from the E2E Slice Engine into “technology-dependent slice enforcement” actions, executed at the data plane level to create, delete, or modify slices as needed.

This architecture enables a scalable and flexible approach to managing network slicing in advanced multi-tenant, multi-domain environments, laying the groundwork for a dynamic and responsive 6G infrastructure.

4.3 Policy Enforcer

4.3.1 Policy Enforcer

The Policy Enforcer, available at the FOKUS testbed, is an application function (AF) designed by FOKUS and used to enforce different policies for UEs for efficient connectivity and data routing. The AF is based on 3GPP release 16 specifications and supports the Traffic Influence API with UEs identified by IP address. During the project, the AF will be extended to push QoS-related policies.

The AF supports the creation and deletion of different subscriptions. These could be triggered by the integrated command module or by the JSON-RPC API. The NEF of Open5GCore supports the identification of UE by IP address. Hence the request from AF has to use the identification of UE by its IP address. The NEF in the initial version supports traffic influence API as specified in ETSI TS 129.522 v16.10.0, and IT is planned to be extended to support QoS enforcement and identification of UE by GPSI (Generic Public Subscription Identifier). The flow of the request is shown in Figure 64 below.

The AF sends a traffic influence request to NEF with details like the IP address of the UE and DNS to switch to. Upon receiving the request, NEF adds the request to the subscription table and translates the received data to the Npcf_PolicyAuthorization object for further processing. However, in case of any error on the server side, status code 500 is sent, or error codes specified in the specifications are sent. In case of successful handling, 204 is sent.

Once NEF handles the request, it sends the request to PCF for policy creation and pushes the policies to SMF, which enforces them and pushes appropriate rules on the UPF for updating the data path. This changes the gateway for the given UE traffic without any triggers from the UE.

The following example enables to trigger subscription creation from AF to NEF:

```
curl -v -X POST -H "Content-Type: application/json-rpc" -d '{"jsonrpc": "2.0", "method": "remote_command.cmd", "params":{"command_name": "af_5g.traffic_influence_create_subscription_w_ip", "command_parameters":"192.168.6.1 dnai2 afl"}, "id": 1}' http://127.0.0.1:10010/jsonrpc
```


Figure 64: Traffic Influences subscription flow chart

API example to trigger subscription creation from AF to NEF:

```
curl -v -X POST -H "Content-Type: application/json-rpc" -d '{"jsonrpc": "2.0", "method": "remote_command.cmd", "params":{"command_name": "af_5g.traffic_influence_create_subscription_w_ip", "command_parameters":"192.168.6.1 dnai2 af1"}, "id": 1}' http://127.0.0.1:10010/jsonrpc
```

4.3.2 ONEmNEF

The ONEmNEF (OneSource’s Microservice-based Network Exposure Function) serves as the Policy Enforcer within the IT testbed, enabling secure, efficient interactions between external Application Functions (AFs) and the 5G Core (5GC). Built on a scalable, cloud-native microservice architecture, it aligns with 3GPP Releases 16 and 17⁵⁵, facilitating dynamic orchestration and secure network exposure to authorised third-party applications. Beyond its role in network exposure, ONEmNEF enforces policies to ensure AF compliance with predefined network policies, offering advanced features such as QoS Control and Traffic Influence.

The integration of the Network Exposure Function in question can be divided into three main sections: the standard NEF API, the possible AFs supported by the testbed that will take advantage of the NEF’s capabilities, and the 5G Core. Between the external Application Functions (AF) and the NEF, the architecture includes a Load Balancer and a Proxy for the Northbound communication, observing the same on the Southbound communications side.

As shown in Figure 65, the NEF’s “core” comprises several distinct components categorised into four groups: the northbound gateway, southbound gateway, NEF API services, and database-related services. Additionally, a crucial message broker component facilitates communication between services and ensures scalability, as does a database to store requests and subscription data.

The message broker lies at the centre of the NEF architecture, acting as a central hub linking various components. It facilitates the flow of requests from the Northbound Gateway to the Southbound Gateway via the API services, performing necessary validations and payload conversions for core service requests. Utilising a message broker for inter-service communication optimises NEF performance by distributing loads among multiple instances of the same services.

⁵⁵ See: <https://www.3gpp.org/specifications-technologies/releases/release-17>

Figure 65: ONEmNEF High-Level Architecture

For the Initial release of the Policy Enforcer, the NEF will support the following two Northbound APIs:

1. **QoS Control**

The Quality of Service (QoS) Control service manages requests to create sessions with the specified QoS parameters [6].

When an AF intends to initiate, update, or terminate a session with particular QoS requirements, it sends a request to the NEF. Upon receiving this request, the NEF diligently verifies the payload for validity. If the payload meets the necessary criteria, the NEF will transmit a corresponding request to the Policy Control Function (PCF) to establish the session and align the QoS settings. This involves carefully mapping values from the AF's request to the new request intended for the PCF. Conversely, if the request is invalid, the NEF promptly responds with a "400 Bad Request" status [7].

Figure 666: QoS control sequence diagram

Upon receiving a response from the PCF, the NEF takes the appropriate action based on the outcome. If the PCF successfully fulfils the request, the NEF creates an "AsSessionWithQoSSubscription" resource. Subsequently, the NEF responds to the AF, conveying this resource within the response payload. If the PCF returns an error code during the process, the NEF promptly informs the AF of the relevant error details [8].

While the subscription remains active, the NEF stands ready to receive notifications. As notifications are received, the NEF acts as a conduit, forwarding these messages to the AF, thus maintaining seamless communication. For a visual representation of this process, refer to Figure 66, which clearly illustrates the described workflow.

2. Traffic Influence

The Traffic Influence service plays a crucial role in handling requests from Application Functions that pertain to the creation, update, or deletion of a "TrafficInfluenceSubscription". Upon receiving the POST request specifically for creating a subscription, a validation process is initiated. If the request is invalid, the Network Exposure Function responds promptly with a "400 Bad Request" status code. Conversely, when the request is valid, the NEF takes distinct actions depending on the nature of the values contained within the payload [9].

If the request is directed towards a single User Equipment (UE), the NEF may retrieve the respective PCF information from the Binding Support Function (BSF). Subsequently, the NEF requests the PCF's "Npcf_PolicyAuthorization" service to create an "ApplicationSessionContext." This entire process is depicted in Figure 67, which visually represents the workflow.

Figure 677: Traffic influence sequence diagram (AF identified by UE address)

In cases where the payload does not contain information identifying the UE address, the NEF interacts with the User Data Management (UDM) function to retrieve either the Subscription Permanent Identifier (SUPI) or the External Group Identifier, depending on whether it involves an individual UE or a group of UEs. Upon successful retrieval, the NEF sends a request to the Unified Data Repository (UDR) through the "Nudr_DataRepository" service. This process is visually represented in Figure 68.

Figure 688: Traffic sequence diagram (AF instance not identified by UE address)

4.4 Close Loop Coordinator

4.4.1 MIRO

Multi-domain Intelligent Resource Orchestration (MIRO) draws inspiration from ETSI Zero-Touch Service Management (ZSM) principles of autonomous service management and closed-loop automation. Still, it is reimagined as a modern Cloud-Native orchestration framework for multi-cluster scenarios. MIRO provides a low-barrier solution for automating Cloud-Native resource management, including applications and infrastructure. More than Cloud-Native, MIRO was designed as a native Kubernetes solution extending the Kubernetes controller and operator paradigms [10] to implement orchestration operations as closed-loop behaviours. Indeed, MIRO integrates various closed loops, each focused on a specific task (e.g., application lifecycle management, infrastructure bootstrapping, or even an AI-driven optimal resource allocation). In this sense, MIRO can resemble a coordinator for closed-loop-based operations. Figure 69 illustrates one of those closed-loop fashion operations leveraging MIRO Kubernetes Custom Resource Definitions (CRDs) used together with a Kubernetes operator (orient) and a custom driver (actuator).

MIRO integrates open-source technologies such as Liqo [11] for multi-cluster interconnection, Cluster API [12] for multi-infrastructure support, and Thanos/Prometheus ([13], [3]), for continuous monitoring of infrastructure and applications. In 6G-PATH, such closed-loop notions and concepts will be explored to allow the conduct of experiments across multi-clusters. This includes the capability to host and run various applications in multi-Kubernetes-based environments, collecting metrics and relevant data during a set period. In the intermediate release, MIRO will provide:

- A graphical interface to define and compose the experiments across testbeds.
- An interface to control and visualise experiments and results, enabling KPI/KVI analysis.
- A KPI/KVI exporter module to export metrics in different formats (e.g., .csv, .json) for post-trial analysis.
- Integration with two clouds.

Figure 699: Infrastructure dedicated close-loop

The final release of the MIRO will focus on exploring the AI-nativeness aspect of the solution as follows.

- Enhanced AI-driven Closed-Loop Automation with refined AI/ML models for operations such as predictive resource scaling and self-healing capabilities.
- API-First design for plug-and-play third-party AI model integration, metrics collection and the possibility to integrate third-party 6G-PATH closed-loops from other partners.
- Improvements in deployment and monitoring functionalities to support more effective execution of experiments.

Table 33: MIRO releases

ID	Monitoring Agents	Due by (Month of Project)
Rel 1	Intermediate Release	M18
Rel 2	Final Release	M24

5 Integration plans for the final release

This section details the high-level integration plans for 6G-PATH. First, Section 6.1 explains the “key” features of each 6G-PATH component and the expected timeline for their development and integration. Later, Section 6.2 focuses on details of planned upgrades and extensions for each testbed.

This section sets the stage for the seamless integration of the 6G-PATH components, establishing the critical link between individual functionalities and the broader vision of a unified, cutting-edge experimentation ecosystem. The integration plans focus on the technical details of each 6G-PATH component and testbed and how they stand in an integrated 6G experimentation platform.

The first part of this section, Section 6.1, delves into the pivotal features of each 6G-PATH component. From the Portal to the advanced monitoring and analytics components, this subsection outlines the role of these building blocks within the ecosystem. Moreover, Section 6.1 provides the timeline for their development and integration, ensuring alignment with project milestones. This highlights the incremental integration strategy (with various releases per component) required to weave them into a cohesive framework, balancing innovation with interoperability.

Section 6.2, on the other hand, focuses on each testbed’s planned upgrades and extensions. The upgrades are not mere refinements—they represent key enhancements designed to extend the functionality of the testbeds, allowing them to accommodate advanced use cases and drive the next wave of 6G experimentation. This includes equipping testbeds with AI-driven analytics, automated monitoring capabilities, and security enforcement mechanisms, ensuring they remain at the forefront of technological advancement. Each upgrade is “tailored” to the specific needs of the testbed, addressing gaps, improving performance, and expanding the potential for collaborative experimentation.

Such a process guarantees the seamless incorporation of each component and testbed into the broader 6G-PATH framework. Furthermore, the integration plans embody a vision beyond immediate implementation, fostering a forward-looking dialogue on harnessing cutting-edge 6G enablers into future research and development.

5.1 6G-PATH framework final release

Figure 70 represents the architecture and functional components of a 6G-PATH framework designed for advanced experimentation and infrastructure management. Below is an introduction to the new components included in the final release:

- **6G-PATH Portal:** This provides a unified management and configuration environment and serves as the primary interface for users to access 6G-PATH functionalities.
- **6G-PATH Northbound Interface:** Provides APIs and interfaces to enable integration with external systems and services.
- **AAA (Authentication, Authorization and Accounting):** This department is responsible for user and service authentication, ensuring secure access, and accounting for resources.
- **Image Repository:** A central repository for storing system and application images for deployment.
- **6G-PATH Testbed Repository:** A repository containing configurations, experiments, and related resources for testbed management.

This layered architecture ensures modularity, scalability, and flexibility, supporting diverse experimentation scenarios and enabling seamless integration with various tools and infrastructures. This section describes the final components of the 6G-PATH framework.

Figure 70: 6G-PATH framework final version

5.1.1 6G-PATH Portal

The 6G-PATH Portal is the primary entry point for users who want to interact with the 6G-PATH testbeds. It is a front-end interface that enables users to authenticate, select and manage testbed experiments.

The indicative figures that follow depict the initial design of the 6G-PATH Portal. Figure 71 below shows the initial “sign in” page of the 6G-PATH Portal, where the user enters their credentials as part of the authentication process. Figure 72 shows the “MyTestbeds2” page, where users may select the testbed on which they can run tests.

The experimenter can see the list of experiments executed and select one to access the analytic module to visualise the analysis of the results (see Figure 73) or decide to start a new experiment. In this case, the experimenter will be redirected to the ELCM Portal to define, configure, and run a new test.

Figure 71: 6G-PATH Portal sign-in

Figure 72: List of testbeds

Figure 73: List experiments/trials executed

Figure 74: Analytics dashboard

The intermediate release of the Portal is expected to provide:

- Integration with the AAA module for user authentication and testbed access: Users can securely log in, verify credentials, and view available testbeds.
- Experiment management: Basic features to start and monitor experiments with status updates.
- Testbed documentation: Essential guidance materials for users.

The final release of the Portal is expected to be fully integrated with the back-end components to expose the following functionality to the user:

- Expanded experiment control: Customization options and advanced parameter settings.
- Real-time monitoring and analytics: Visualizations to track performance and outcomes.
- User and access management: Role and permission settings for collaborative setups.
- Third-party integration: Data export and additional analysis capabilities.

- In-portal support: Feedback and support tools for improved user experience.

The fully developed 6G-PATH Portal will simplify user interaction with complex testbed environments, enabling seamless experimentation and management.

Table 34 shows the estimated timeline for the 6G-PATH portal releases, including the intermediate and final release months.

Table 34: 6G-PATH framework Portal releases

ID	6G-PATH Portal	Due by (Month of Project)
Rel 2	Intermediate release	M16
Rel 3	Final release	M24

Figure 755: 6G-PATH Northbound Interface Initial design

5.1.2 6G-PATH Northbound Interface

The 6G-PATH Northbound Interface/API links the 6G-PATH Portal, AAA component, and testbeds to manage user authentication, testbed access, and experiment execution. The initial design of the Northbound Interface, along with its interaction with other components, is depicted in Figure 75.

The intermediate release of the Northbound Interface is expected to provide:

- Basic authentication: It handles user authentication through the AAA system.
- Testbed access: It retrieves accessible testbed URLs for user selection.
- Basic experiment execution: It routes experiment requests to lifecycle engines.

The final release of the Northbound Interface is expected to have:

- Enhanced access control: Advanced permissions for multi-user access.
- Expanded experiment management: Full lifecycle support, including monitoring.
- Performance reporting: Real-time experiment status and error handling.

The final interface will provide secure, streamlined connections for efficient testbed interaction.

The estimated timeline for the Northbound Interface releases is outlined in the Table 35, including both the intermediate and final release months.

Table 35: 6G-PATH Northbound Interface/API Releases

ID	6G-PATH Northbound Interface/API	Due by (Month of Project)
Rel 2	Intermediate release	M13
Rel 3	Final release	M27

5.1.3 AAA

The AAA (Authentication, Authorization and Accounting) component, implemented with Keycloak [14], is the core solution for managing user access and ensuring security within the 6G-PATH architecture. Keycloak handles user authentication by verifying credentials upon login to the portal and granting secure access to the 6G-PATH platform. It also enforces role-based authorisation to control testbed access based on assigned user roles, ensuring that only authorised individuals can run experiments on specific testbeds. Beyond access control, Keycloak's accounting functionality logs user activities and tracks experiment usage, supporting comprehensive auditing and efficient resource management across the platform.

In the intermediate release, the AAA component is expected to include the following core features:

- Basic Authentication: Supports standard authentication protocols to verify user identities.
- Basic Authorisation: Provides initial Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) for determining primary access permissions to different testbeds, ensuring secure experiment execution.
- Single Sign-On (SSO): This feature enables users to log in once and gain access to multiple services within the 6G-PATH experimentation platform, enhancing user convenience.
- Basic Accounting: Tracks user login history and experiment usage data to facilitate basic auditing and resource monitoring.

In the final release, the AAA component will be enhanced with additional functionalities to support a more sophisticated security and access management system:

- Advanced Authentication Options: expands support for social logins (e.g., Google, GitHub) for more flexible user access options.
- Comprehensive Accounting and Logging: Tracks detailed user activity logs, including experiment usage, duration, and testbed interactions, for in-depth auditing and resource management.
- User and Role Management: Provides intuitive interfaces for managing user roles and permissions, enabling collaborative setups with precise access control for each user or group.

Table 36: 6G-PATH AAA Releases

ID	6G-PATH AAA	Due by (Month of Project)
Rel 1	Intermediate release	M14
Rel 2	Final release	M24

5.1.4 Image Repository

The Image Repository is a key component of the 6G-PATH experimentation framework for managing and storing use case images used for experiments conducted across the various testbeds. The repository ensures that the

required use case images are available to the 6G-PATH Experiment Lifecycle Manager (ELCM) for testbed deployment. GitLab is the central platform for managing the complete lifecycle of use case images and associated experiments. Users can interact with GitLab via the UI and the Git CLI for direct version control. GitLab’s CI/CD pipeline facilitates image deployment automation. Once changes are pushed to the repository, the pipeline automatically builds the images, runs validation checks, and, if successful, pushes them to the centralised 6G-PATH Use Case Image Repository. From here, the ELCM can be triggered to deploy the images onto the appropriate testbed for further experimentation. GitLab’s pipeline can also be configured to run specific test scripts, allowing the evaluation of image performance and functionality before deployment.

In the intermediate release, the Image Repository will provide the following features/functionality:

- Basic image storage and management (including image upload/download, version control, and metadata management)
- User access and permissions – Integration with authentication systems to control access to the repository.
- Basic interface with the ELCM so the stored images can be retrieved and deployed to the testbeds.

The final release of the Image Repository will build on the functionality of the intermediate release, adding advanced features where necessary to improve usability and ensure better integration. The following improvements are envisioned:

- Advanced image management and organisation with enhanced metadata functionality and more granular classifications for images.
- Scalability and performance optimisation to ensure the repository can scale to accommodate large volumes of images.
- Provide CI/CD pipelines to ensure repositories can efficiently handle high loads.

Table 37: 6G-Image Repository releases

ID	6G-PATH Image Repository	Due by (Month of Project)
Rel 1	Intermediate release	M15
Rel 2	Final release	M24

5.1.5 6G-PATH testbed repository

The Testbed Repository is a centralised storage system within the 6G-PATH architecture that maintains URLs and metadata for all registered testbeds. It enables the Northbound Interface to retrieve accurate details for authorised users. It holds information on each testbed’s monitoring databases, which support collecting and visualising experiment metrics. This repository ensures efficient management and access to available testbeds and monitoring resources.

In the intermediate release, the Testbed Repository will provide the following essential features:

- **Basic Testbed Registration and Storage:** This service stores URLs and metadata for each registered testbed, allowing basic testbed information to be accessible within the 6G-PATH platform.
- **Accessible via REST API:** Supports basic REST API operations to retrieve testbed information for authorised users, specifically:
 - `GET /testbeds/{id}`: Returns a list of testbeds available to the authenticated user, with associated URLs and basic details.

The final release of the Testbed Repository will introduce advanced capabilities, building on the intermediate features to deliver a more robust and user-friendly experience:

- **Enhanced Testbed Metadata:** Includes additional metadata fields for each testbed, such as supported experiment types, hardware specifications, and connectivity options, providing a more comprehensive view of testbed resources.

- Enhanced Access Control and Role Management: Works with the AAA component to ensure that only authorised users can access testbed metadata and enables detailed control over user permissions per testbed.

Table 38: 6G-PATH Testbed Repository releases

ID	6G-PATH Testbed Repository	Due by (Month of Project)
Rel 1	Intermediate release	M15
Rel 2	Final release	M24

5.1.6 6G-PATH Analytics

The **Analytics** will follow a decentralised approach, where each testbed is responsible for independently deploying the required dashboard modules. Detailed deployment instructions will be provided for each testbed owner to ensure consistency. The **Analytics** collects data and calculates **KPIs (and/or KVIs if applicable)**. The Analytics will retrieve data from each testbed's 6G-PATH Monitoring Database (e.g., **InfluxDB**), calculating KPIs/KVIs based on the Experiment ID provided by the **ELCM**. The Experiment ID, supplied by the ELCM, allows users to select KPIs associated with specific testbed experiments they are authorised to access.

The front-end of the Analytics is a dashboard for data visualisation, which will graphically render the KPIs/KVIs and experiment metrics. This dashboard will allow users to interactively select KPIs/KVIs and visualise data from the experiments they conducted. The Analytics dashboard will be seamlessly integrated with the 6G-PATH Northbound Interface, ensuring that users can only access and visualise data from the testbeds they are authorised to use, as verified by the AAA component.

Each testbed will maintain its own **Monitoring Database** for storing the experiment data, which will be retrieved by the Analytics for KPI/KVI calculation and visualisation purposes. While the data collected will vary across testbeds, the information will follow a standardised structure, ensuring consistency and interoperability in storing and visualising the data. Although certain testbeds will offer **unique metrics** based on their specific infrastructure, there will also be a set of **common KPIs/KVIs** across all testbeds. This unified data structure will be formalised to streamline the querying, calculation, and visualisation processes, enabling a coherent user experience across the 6G-PATH testbed ecosystem.

In the intermediate release, based on the information received from the mature testbed, our goal is to provide the necessary tools for the testbed to deploy the data collector within their facilities. In the final release, we will have integrated all testbeds with the REST endpoints and tools we provide (Docker Compose, K8s YAML files, and Helm Charts) for the data collector to transfer KPIs to the Portal for visualization. Throughout the process, we will provide continuous support to each testbed.

The backend Analytics service, implemented as a Spring Boot application, is an intermediary between the frontend dashboard and the InfluxDB database in the testbeds. It provides a REST API endpoint that allows the dashboard to request specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and Key Value Indicators (KVIs) for a given experiment, identified by its execution ID. Upon receiving such a request, the service forwards it to the InfluxDB database, fetches the relevant data, organises it into a standardised JSON format, and returns the processed data to the dashboard.

The Analytics, along with its interaction with other components, is shown in the **Error! Reference source not found.6**.

Table 39: Analytics Releases

ID	6G-PATH Analytics	Due by (Month of Project)
Rel 1	Intermediate release	M15
Rel 2	Final release	M24

Figure 76: 6G-PATH Analytics Dashboard

5.1.7 ELCM

The features planned for the intermediate release of the ELCM are the following:

- **Task coordinator**, to improve parallel task management during the execution of the test cases
- **Task cleanup**, to allow the cancellation of an experiment during its execution, ensuring the release of resources used for the experiment and deleting the instances of the components involved. The task will allow the experimenter to enter the necessary instructions for removing instances of third-party tools used in the experiment.
- To support the **management of scenarios** to manage the configuration of network conditions independently of the execution of the test cases.

The final release will incorporate the fixes identified during the testbed integration phase.

Table 40: ELCM Releases

ID	ELCM	Due by (Month of Project)
Rel 2	Intermediate Release	M18
Rel 3	Final Release	M24

5.1.8 ELCM Portal

The intermediate release of the ELCM Portal will include new features to improve user usability and user management. The final release will incorporate the fixes identified during the testbed integration phase.

Table 41: ELCM Portal Releases

ID	ELCM Portal	Due by (Month of Project)
Rel 2	Intermediate Release	M18

Rel 3	Final Release	M24
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5.1.9 Influx and Grafana

The features planned for the intermediate release are the following:

- Adapt the ELCM to work with the latest version of Grafana.
- Allow Grafana to work with both V1 and V2 versions of InfluxDB.

The final release will incorporate the fixes identified during the testbed integration phase.

Table 42: Influx and Grafana Updates

ID	Influx and Grafana	Due by (Month of Project)
Rel 2	Intermediate Release	M18
Rel 3	Final Release	M24

5.1.10 Common Monitoring Tools

The features planned for the intermediate release are the following:

- To migrate monitoring Agents for PC to Linux
- To update TAP plugins for the automation of the agents

The final release will incorporate the fixes identified during the testbed integration phase.

Table 43: Monitoring Agent Releases

ID	Monitoring Agents	Due by (Month of Project)
Rel 2	Intermediate Release	M18
Rel 3	Final Release	M24

5.2 Testbed upgrades, extensions and timeline

This section introduces each platform's timeline for the planned updates and integrations. It also provides the plans for providing the final advanced features at the different testbeds. Figure 77 summarises the advanced features the different testbeds offer in the final release.

Figure 77: 6G-PATH advanced experimentation features for the final release

5.2.1 ORO testbed

ORO considers the following upgrade activities for the duration of the 6G-PATH project. Multiple upgrade and extension activities will be performed simultaneously, and the implementation status will be available in the project's reporting and deliverables.

The timeline for implementation has been running since Month 4 of 6G-PATH (April 2024), and confirmation of implementation is expected by Month 24 of 6G-PATH (December 2025), enabling the onboarding, testing, and experimentation activities in WP6.

Table 44: Timeline for the implementation of upgrades and extensions in the ORO testbed

ID	Upgrade / Extension	Due by
EXT1	Extend 5G SA coverage to new locations to include the geographical areas of the Use-Case beneficiaries (the two rural schools)	M20
UPG1	E2E Network Slice definition for UC-EDU-1	M20
UPG2	gNBs and UPF implementation	M21
EXT2	Extend EDGE cluster to end-users service deployment location for UC-EDU-1	M22
UPG3	New 5G XR device acquisition and validation for usage in the 6G Testbed	M16
UPG4	5G/6G network configuration and slice adaptation for UC traffic requirements	M20
UPG5	APIs and Adaptors implementation for dynamic network configuration and services deployment	M22
EXT3	Interfaces definition, development and integration for the integration with the 6G-PATH Service Framework	M18
UPG6	Local EDGE/UPF and slice implementation, slice configuration	M22
UPG7	5G SBA with CP/UP separation and 5G slice deployment with EDGE support	M22
EXT4	6G-PATH network and services KPIs and data collection, and exposure to app layers (for 3 rd party experimenters)	M18
EXT5	E2E 6G-PATH assets / KERs integration, testing and validation of functionality	M24

5.2.2 OTE testbed

OTE testbed will be upgraded in 3 main directions:

- Network architecture upgrade: The current version includes Rel.16 functions. However, the functions are planned to be enriched with new ones, improving the capabilities of the RAN, e.g., in end-to-end slicing.
- Monitoring: The testbed's monitoring tool will be installed to collect network KPI measurements. Probes to collect data and the server that will host the tool will be integrated into the network infrastructure. Additionally, a local instance of ELCM will be installed.
- Slicing mechanism: The current slicing mechanism is static. However, an automated one has been designed. Poor network performance will be detected by analysing the collected network performance data (latency, throughput, packet loss). Then, decision-making algorithms or AI tools will be able to request the slice change from the slice manager.

Table 45: Timeline for the implementation of upgrades and extensions in the OTE testbed

ID	Upgrade / Extension	Due by
UPG1	5G network upgrade: RAN upgrade in progress	M15
UPG2	Slicing manager upgrade	M18
EXT1	ELCM local installation	M14

EXT2	Testbed’s monitoring tool installation	M13
EXT3	Slicing mechanism close loop	M24

5.2.3 UMA testbed

A satellite connection will be installed at the La Mayora experimental farm to serve as the backhaul for the 5G private network deployed on-site. This setup will ensure that the internet access for the 5G private network is isolated from the fibre optic connection used for other purposes. Additionally, it simulates a realistic scenario in which no fixed connections are available for remote access in rural or remote areas. The satellite connection will support the remote management of the 5G private network and the operation of the deployed use cases. It will also enable access to the data collected by sensors and the images captured by multispectral cameras.

The satellite connection is targeted to be operational by February 2025. Additionally, additional 5G routers are planned to interconnect the existing infrastructure at the farm with the 5G network by April 2025. The remaining upgrades and extensions are detailed in Table 46.

Table 46: Timeline for the implementation of upgrades and extensions in the UMA testbed

ID	Upgrade / Extension	Due by
UPG1	Upgrade EDGE cluster located in La Mayora for the deployment of the use cases	M12
UPG2	E2E Network slicing configuration in La Mayora	M12
EXT1	Deployment of additional 5G routers in new locations	M14
EXT2	Satellite deployment	M14
EXT3	Slice management	M16
EXT3	Closed-loop for slicing	M21

5.2.4 UWS testbed

The UWS Testbed will be part of the UC-EDU-2 Use cases and will benefit from the push required regarding capabilities, requirements, and connectivity for delivering such use cases. The extensions and upgrades listed in Table 47 are foreseen to be executed along the project.

Table 47: Timeline for the implementation of upgrades and extensions in UWS testbed

ID	Upgrade / Extension	Due by
EXT1	Extend the Number of Computational Resources Available for Open Calls	M12
EXT2	E2E Network slicing configuration in the testbed	M16
UPG1	Slice management capabilities updated and exposed as a service	M21
UPG2	Experimentation Portal Upgraded	M21
UPG3	Update OpenAirInterface versions to be compliant with latest 5GPP releases available	M21

5.2.5 FOKUS testbed

The FOKUS testbed will be part of 3D hydrogel patches and Elderly monitoring use cases. In these use cases, a centralised control and data plane will be set up with Open5GCore in the FOKUS testbed for initial PoCs and tests. The changes needed to support these use cases have been identified. These extensions and upgrades are given in Table 48.

Table 48: Timeline for the implementation of upgrades and extensions in UWS testbed

ID	Upgrade / Extension	Due by
UPG1	Update NEF support for QoS extensions	M12
UPG2	Extend slicing support via API	M14
UPG3	Edge deployment in 3D hydrogel path use case	M18

EXT1	Add a new Wireguard network for 6G-PATH	M14
EXT2	Deploy central core network	M14
EXT3	Deployment of network in use-case locations	M16
EXT3	E2E validation of 6G-PATH functionality	M24

5.2.6 KAU testbed

The testbed is the central location for implementing the XR health training use case in the project. This use case focuses on enhancing the training of ambulance nurses by providing more realistic training scenarios and allowing students to participate in training remotely in an immersive way. For this use case and related use cases in the health and education domain, the following components have been identified as potential essential extensions for the testbed.

Table 49: Timeline for the implementation of upgrades and extensions in KAU testbed

ID	Upgrade / Extension	Due by
EXT1	Extend the testbed with outdoor coverage	M12
EXT2	Exposure of core functions via NEF-based API and CAMARA	M18
EXT3	A DNN offering Starlink Internet access from the local breakout.	M20
UPG1	Enhanced solutions for positioning	M22
UPG2	Radio enhancement for XR services or other low latency enhancements (tentative)	M24

5.2.7 ALB/IT testbed

The ALB/IT testbed plans the extensions and upgrades described in Table 50.

Table 50: Timeline for the implementation of upgrades and extensions in ALB/IT testbed

ID	Upgrade / Extension	Due by
EXT1	NEF (ONE) and OpenAPI support (Telefonica)	M12
UPG1	New servers datacenter and upgraded edge computing	M14
EXT2	Extend the testbed with additional city points and controlled zone for autonomous vehicles	M18
EXT3	New USRP modules to extend the SDR RAN to more testbed sites	M18
UPG2	Live!Urban	M14
UPG3	Slice management	M18
EXT4	TSN capabilities and more IoT sensors (fixed and mobile)	M24
EXT5	AI as a Service (AlaaS)	M24
EXT6	E2E validation of 6G-PATH functionality	M24

6 Conclusions

The first version of the 6G-PATH experimental testbeds is essential in defining the 6G-PATH experimental framework that spans the various testbeds being developed as part of the project. This deliverable highlights the testbed's readiness for experiments and the incorporation of the critical elements of the framework required for carrying out experiments, validations, and trials.

The deployment builds on advanced features such as network slicing, policy management, security as a service and integrated monitoring capabilities to position the 6G-PATH framework for large-scale novel experimentation. Also, it includes the Experiment Lifecycle Manager (ELCM) to realise experiment and trial management and complete integration of monitoring and analytics tools to facilitate experiment execution. Collectively, these aspects improve the platform's flexibility to address new research needs and emerging technological trends.

In subsequent phases, the project will scale these features, starting by extending additional testbeds, improving API capabilities, provisioning more complex scenarios and enhancing AI-based services.

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Annex I: Manual for the Influx Data Pipeline

This annex shows a user manual for the Influx Data Pipeline. The manual explains how to perform the installation process and how to use the tool normally.

Installation

1. Clone the repository to a known, e.g. in /InfluxDataPipeline
2. Enter the folder

```
cd ./InfluxDataPipeline
```

For the configuration a file called `config.yml` will be created after the first start of the program. In this file the sensitive data related to the InfluxDB instance such address, access token and organization must be specified. This file will be created empty if it does not exist so that it can be filled in by the administrator.

Scripts for Linux “install.sh” and Windows “instsal.ps1” as well as scripts to start the application “start.sh” “start.ps1” will be provided for the installation for your convenience.

In the installation script you must enter the python interpreter to be used as well as the necessary parameters for the

initial configuration, being the format

```
install.sh <python-interpreter> <url> <org> <token>
```

i.e.: ./install.sh python3.11 http://localhost:8086 UMA token

If you do not want to use the scripts, you can always perform a manual setup as follows.

1. Create a new Python virtualenv

```
Python -m venv ./venv
```
2. Activate the virtual environment:
 - For Windows

```
venv/Scripts/Activate.bat
```
 - For Linux

```
Source venv/bin/activate
```
3. Install Python dependencies:

```
pip install -r requirements.txt
```
4. Start the development server, you can use the `-p` flag to set the port

```
flask run
```

The app will start listening for requests on port 5000. Press `Ctrl-C` to stop the development server.

5. At the first startup we will get an error indicating that the fields of the *config.yml* file created are not filled in if you don't use the install script with the proper flags. After filling it with the corresponding information the *InfluxDataPipeline* must be restarted.

Usage

A typical use of the tool involves accessing the address exposed by the Flask server via a browser. The interface displayed allows you to enter the required metadata and select the CSV files to be written. The tool supports uploading one or multiples CSVs files, which will then be written to the specified InfluxDB database. Optionally, extra tags can also be added to identify the experiment. The tool is compatible with InfluxDB V2. Before writing, the tool performs checks to ensure that the file size is within the allowed limits, the file extension is correct, and the file names follow the expected format.

The *InfluxDataPipeline* also exposes an endpoint */write_csv* for making requests via REST calls in form format. The request must be a multipart/form-data where the metadata will be entered in the form of JSON in the metadata field and the csv files in the file fields indicated. An example of a possible query to run with the curl tool:

```
curl --location http://127.0.0.1:5000/write_csv
--form "metadata=@path-to-metadata.json"
--form "file=@path-to-file1.csv"
--form "file=@path-to-file2.csv"
--form "file=@path-to-file3.csv"
```

The following is an explanation of the fields that will be included in the JSON file with the metadata:

- **bucket** (String): The name of the InfluxDB bucket where the data from the CSVs will be written. The bucket must already exist in the database before writing the data
- **measurement** (String): The name of the measurement in InfluxDB where the data will be stored. If the measurement does not exist, it will be created automatically
- **execution_id** (String): A tag or unique identifier user to group data points in InfluxDB for a specific execution or experiment
- **time_name** (String): The name of the column in the CSV file that contains the timestamp (usually in ISO-8086 format)
- **delimiter** (String): The character used to separate fields in the CSV file(e.g., for comma or ; for semicolon)
- **time_format** (String): The format string for the time values, which should be compatible with Python's [strftime](#) function from the datetime library i.e.: %Y-%m-%dT%H:%M:%S.%fZ
- **extra_tags** (Dictionary): Optional dictionary with extra tags to identify the experiment. They must be expressed as key, value.

An example of such a file is in the sample folder under the name "*sample/metadata-example.json*".